

Dissemination Report (first version)

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Abstract

This deliverable provides the first dissemination report of the RESCALE project, covering the period from Month 1 to Month 18. It presents the strategy, tools and activities used to communicate RESCALE's vision and results, including digital outreach, scientific publications, promotional materials and participation in key events.

The report highlights the project's growing visibility, engagement across multiple stakeholder groups and early collaborations with related initiatives. It also reflects on challenges encountered and lessons learned, setting the direction for enhanced dissemination in the second half of the project and supporting RESCALE's mission to secure supply chains.

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List of Abbreviations

- API** Application Programming Interface. 28
- CD** Continuous Development. 23
- CI** Continuous Integration. 23
- CWE** Common Weakness Enumeration. 29
- DCP** Dissemination and Communication Plan. 41, 42, 48
- DoA** Description of Action. 37
- DSCG** Dynamic Supply Chain component Guarantee. 23, 24
- FPGA** Field-Programmable Gate Array. 28
- GDPR** General Data Protection Regulation. 10
- KPI** Key Performance Indicator. 7, 9, 22, 23, 25, 30, 37–41, 43–45, 48
- ML** Machine Learning. 24, 27, 28
- MVP** Minimum Viable Product. 40–42, 45
- ROP** Return-oriented programming. 24
- SBOM** Software Bill of Materials. 29
- TBOM** Trusted Bill of Materials. 7, 23, 26, 29
- WP** Work Package. 6, 37, 43–45

1 Introduction

The RESCALE project aims to design, build and demonstrate secure-by-design supply chains. The project concentrates on automating the assessment of security for hardware and software components, verifying the reliability of third-party elements, and implementing robust auditing and testing procedures. In an increasingly interconnected digital environment, RESCALE aims to ensure the security and resilience of supply chains by protecting system components from vulnerabilities, safeguarding sensitive data and enabling secure, trustworthy system development across hardware and software layers.

Dissemination plays a crucial role in the project, ensuring that RESCALE's key findings, technological advancements and research outputs are effectively communicated to a wide range of audiences and reach several key stakeholder groups. By promoting transparency and fostering knowledge transfer, dissemination activities help maximize the project's impact and contribute to advancing cybersecurity best practices. The deliverable is situated between D6.1 which established the project's website and the upcoming D6.3, which will provide the final dissemination report.

1.1 Scope & Contribution

This deliverable serves two main objectives:

- To document and assess the dissemination activities conducted in the first half of the project, evaluating their reach and effectiveness.
- To outline the approach for ongoing dissemination for the remainder of the project, ensuring continued alignment with the project's objectives and stakeholder engagement needs.

This deliverable specifically covers the period **from Month 1 (October 2023) to Month 18 (March 2025)**, corresponding to the first half of the project's duration and the **first reporting period**.

As part of WP6, this report provides transparency on outreach efforts, offering a structured overview of how dissemination activities have supported knowledge transfer, engagement with industry, academia, policymakers, and the broader cybersecurity and supply chain security communities. By analyzing both qualitative and quantitative dissemination metrics, this deliverable reflects on the effectiveness of past dissemination efforts and highlights key areas of focus for the remainder of the project to ensure that RESCALE's outputs achieve maximum visibility and impact across relevant stakeholder groups.

1.2 Relation to Work Packages, Deliverables, and Activities

Dissemination is interconnected with multiple Work Packages (WPs), deliverables and project activities to ensure effective communication of RESCALE's results. While WP6 is responsible

for dissemination, it relies on technical developments and findings from other WPs to provide content for outreach.

Relation to Work Packages

- **WP3 - Static and Dynamic Analysis Testing:** WP3 is responsible for developing security testing tools, including static code analysis, dynamic analysis and hardware vulnerability detection. These outputs provide critical research contributions that feed into scientific publications, technical presentations and stakeholder engagement activities.
- **WP4 - Trusted Supply Chain Establishment:** WP4 focuses on enhancing supply chain security through the development of the Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) as well as the design and implementation of associated security and trust mechanisms. The methodologies and frameworks introduced in WP4 contribute to dissemination efforts through research papers, technical reports and industry outreach.
- **WP5 - Integration, Deployment and Validation:** WP5 plays a key role in validating and demonstrating RESCALE technologies in real-world scenarios. These practical implementations generate results that are crucial for dissemination efforts, reinforcing the project's impact on cybersecurity and supply chain security.

Relation to Deliverables

D6.2 is a key deliverable in WP6 and is closely related to “**D6.1: Project Website**”¹, which describes the project website that serves as the project's primary communication hub. The website plays a crucial role in disseminating project updates, announcements and public deliverables, ensuring visibility.

Additionally, this report sets the foundation for “**D6.3: Dissemination Report (final version)**”, which will assess dissemination activities for the second half of the project and outline the strategy for sustaining impact beyond the project's duration.

Relation to Activities

The dissemination activities covered in this report include scientific publications, conference participation, online engagement and stakeholder interactions, all of which are strategically aligned with the project's milestones. These efforts ensure that RESCALE's findings and technological advancements reach academic, industrial and policy-making audiences, maximizing visibility and impact.

1.3 Contribution to WP6 and Project Objectives

This deliverable plays a central role in WP6, as it provides an evaluative perspective on dissemination efforts and ensures that outreach strategies remain effective and aligned with the project's broader objectives. Key contributions include:

- Assessing the impact of dissemination activities conducted during the first half of the project (M1-M18), based on preliminary KPIs.

¹<https://rescale-project.eu>

- Enhancing transparency in how RESCALE shares its findings with external stakeholders, for example by publishing project deliverables and outcomes on open-access platforms such as Zenodo.
- Ensuring strategic alignment between dissemination actions and overall project goals.
- Providing insights and recommendations for refining dissemination strategies based on lessons learned in M1-M18.
- Reporting on the progress of the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

By effectively reporting on dissemination activities and refining outreach strategies, **D6.2** contributes to RESCALE's goal of establishing cybersecurity best practices in supply chain security through sustained knowledge transfer and stakeholder engagement. D6.2 also aligns with the objectives of WP6, particularly raising awareness and maximizing visibility and impact through structured dissemination efforts (O6.1).

1.4 Structure of the Document

This deliverable is structured to provide a comprehensive overview of the dissemination and communication activities conducted during the first reporting period of the RESCALE project. The document is organized as follows:

- **Section 1 – Introduction:** Presents the scope of the deliverable, its relation to relevant work packages and deliverables, contribution to WP6 objectives, intended audience and an overview of the document structure.
- **Section 2 – Communication Channels and Tools:** Details the various channels utilized for dissemination, including the project website, social media platforms, media outreach, newsletters and promotional materials.
- **Section 3 – Scientific and Technical Dissemination:** Highlights scientific publications in peer-reviewed venues, participation in conferences and workshops, collaboration with other EU-funded projects, and networking activities undertaken to promote project results.
- **Section 4 – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Impact Assessment:** Provides an overview of dissemination-related KPIs and evaluates the effectiveness and impact of the project's dissemination strategy.
- **Section 5 – Conclusions and Future Steps:** Summarizes key findings, identifies challenges and lessons learned, and outlines planned future dissemination activities to ensure continued visibility and stakeholder engagement.
- **Appendix A – Dissemination and Communication Plan:** Presents the internal report on the dissemination and communication plan, which describes the target audiences and stakeholders, outlines key communication goals and summarizes the planned dissemination activities guiding the project's outreach efforts.

2 Communication Channels and Tools

Effective communication channels and tools are essential for ensuring RESCALE's visibility, stakeholder engagement and dissemination impact. These channels enable the timely and structured dissemination of project objectives, results and updates, ensuring that relevant audiences are consistently informed. A combination of digital platforms, promotional materials and targeted outreach methods has been employed to maximize reach and engagement. This section provides an overview of the platforms and materials utilized to communicate project progress and key outcomes to a broad audience.

2.1 Project Website

The official RESCALE project website, which uses the domain name rescale-project.eu, serves as the primary communication hub for sharing the project's objectives, progress and public outcomes with stakeholders, industry, academia and the general public. It is designed to ensure transparency, accessibility and consistent engagement throughout the project's lifecycle.

2.1.1 Website Overview

The website was developed in the early stages of the project (by Month 3), as described in deliverable D6.1, and is regularly updated to reflect new developments in the project. Its structure includes dedicated sections presenting the project's vision, objectives, consortium partners, use cases, news, events, public deliverables, publications and dissemination materials following a user-centric approach. A short explanation of each page in RESCALE's website is given below.

- **Home:** Includes short descriptions of the project's scope, goal and key concepts.
- **Objectives:** Highlights the project's vision and key objectives. The project's high-level up to date architecture is also presented in this page.
- **Use Cases:** Provides in-depth information about the two use cases of the project by PST and CC.
- **Consortium:** Lists all project partners, their logos and links to their websites.
- **Dissemination:** This page hosts the dissemination material of the project. It includes all conference and journal publications made, newsletters, posters, leaflets/brochures and non-confidential deliverables approved by the European Commission. For each of those, links are included that point to Zenodo, ensuring open-access compliance. Downloads and views of these materials on Zenodo are actively monitored, and they directly contribute to RESCALE's dissemination KPIs, as detailed in Section 4.2 of this report. The events organized and attended by the consortium are also included, as well as future planned events.
- **Blog/News:** This page serves as both a news and a blog page. It features blog articles about RESCALE and updates about major project events and milestones.

- **Contact:** Allows stakeholders and visitors to directly reach the consortium by submitting the contact form with their details.
- **Privacy Policy:** This page outlines how personal data is collected, processed and protected in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It describes the rights of users, how data is used and who to contact for privacy-related concerns. It also includes additional relevant information. The full privacy policy is available at <https://rescale-project.eu/privacy-policy>.
- **Cookie Policy:** This page provides detailed information about the cookies used on the RESCALE website, their purpose (e.g., analytics, etc.) and how users can manage their preferences. It also includes additional relevant information about cookies and the RESCALE website handles them. The cookie policy is accessible at <https://rescale-project.eu/cookie-policy-eu/>.

2.1.2 Website Updates

During the reporting period (M1-M18), several significant updates and improvements have been made to enhance the website’s functionality, content and user engagement.

A major structural update involved the merging of the blog page with the news page, consolidating all blog articles and project news into a single, easily navigable section. This change simplifies content access for visitors and streamlines the management of updates. The combined page now presents all published blog articles and news items, ensuring a unified experience for users seeking the latest information on RESCALE’s progress. The content is also easily distinguishable, allowing users to navigate easily.

Another major update was the creation of a cookie consent banner. The banner appears immediately when users visit the website, allowing them to accept or reject non-essential cookies in compliance with EU regulations. Figure 1 shows the design of the banner. The design is subject to change.

Figure 1: Website - Cookie Banner

Further content updates implemented during the reporting period include:

- Publication of project news articles, plenary meeting summaries, and updates on key events.
- Upload of the initial public deliverables alongside corresponding links to the RESCALE Zenodo community, ensuring open-access availability.
- Announcements regarding the project's participation in workshops, conferences and external collaborations.
- Regular updates reflecting partner contributions, technical advancements, and major milestones achieved.

To improve usability and foster engagement, several continuous improvement actions have also been undertaken:

- Streamlined navigation, particularly for quicker access to deliverables and publications.
- Consistent application of project branding and visual elements across all pages to strengthen recognition.
- Links to social media accounts were added to enhance cross-platform visibility and provide users with access to real-time updates.
- Addition of direct links to newsletters, press releases, and other dissemination materials to centralize access for visitors.

These updates ensure that the RESCALE website remains a dynamic and reliable platform for communication, effectively supporting dissemination objectives and stakeholder engagement throughout the project's lifecycle. The improvements are also aligned with the stakeholder engagement and user experience principles outlined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan in Annex A, particularly with respect to accessibility, responsiveness and user-centric design.

2.1.3 Website Analytics

Monitoring website analytics is essential to evaluate the effectiveness of the project's online presence and to ensure that dissemination efforts are reaching the intended audiences. By analyzing key metrics, the consortium can assess engagement levels, identify areas for improvement and adjust communication strategies accordingly.

The website's performance is continuously tracked using the WP-Statistics plugin [13]. The statistics analyzed in this section cover the period from December 2 2023, to March 21 2025, corresponding to the time since the website was initially launched. Some of the key metrics evaluated include total page visits or views, unique visitors, most visited pages, geographical

reach (where visitors are primarily from), and traffic sources (direct access, social media referrals, search engine queries, etc.). Figures presenting the collected website statistics over this period are shown below.

Figure 2: Website Analytics - Traffic Trend

Figure 2 illustrates the website’s traffic trend from December 2023 to March 2025 (as explained previously, since December is the time that the website was up and running). It shows a total of 4,403 unique visitors and 9,971 page views during this period. A significant increase in traffic is observed between March and August 2024, correlated with increased dissemination activities and promotion of the website. Following this peak, the trend stabilizes with consistent monthly engagement.

Most Visited Pages ⓘ

Page	Views
Home Page: RESCALE	3,761
Blog / News	781
Objectives	378
Consortium	354
News	273
Press Releases	255
Use Cases	247
Dissemination	179
Publications	159
RESCALE Kick-off Meeting	142

Figure 3: Website Analytics - Most Visited Pages

Figure 3 presents the distribution of the most visited pages. The Home page received the highest number of views (3,761 views), followed by the Blog/News page (781 views) and the Objectives page (378 views).

Country	Visitor Count	View Count
China	1,308	2,237
United States	1,264	2,290
Greece	422	2,470
Germany	216	290
Singapore	157	212
Netherlands	103	163
United Kingdom	85	207
Finland	68	96
Ireland	66	155
France	56	118

Figure 4: Website Analytics - Geographical Distribution

Figure 4 details the geographical distribution of website visitors. The majority of visitors originated from China (1,308 visits), followed closely by the United States (1,264 visits) and Greece (422 visits). The second column of Figure 4 shows the total number of views from the countries. Additionally, notable engagement was recorded from Germany, Singapore and the Netherlands, indicating broad international interest in RESCALE's activities.

Figure 5: Website Analytics - Geographical Distribution Map

Figure 5 visually represents the global distribution of visitors. The highlighted regions correspond to the highest engagement levels, supporting the numerical data presented previously. The 1308 number in Figure 5 represents the number of visitors from China, which is the top country in terms of visitor count to the RESCALE website supporting the numerical data.

Domain Address	Number of Referrals ↓
https://rescale-project.eu	472
https://rescale-project.eu/	219
http://rescale-project.eu	212
http://www.rescale-project.eu	160
https://www.google.com/	124

Figure 6: Website Analytics - Top Referring Domains

Figure 6 highlights the top referring domains driving traffic to the website. The majority of referrals came from direct access or linked sources within the RESCALE domain itself, such as “https://rescale-project.eu” and its subpages. External referrals from search engines like Google (124 total referrals) also contributed significantly, underscoring the visibility of RESCALE content on widely used platforms.

Time	Visitors	Views
Today	3	3
Yesterday	5	18
This week	15	29
Last week	16	25
This month	58	108
Last month	107	289
Last 7 days	16	34
Last 30 days	90	178
Last 90 days	262	578
Last 6 months	594	1.24K
This year (Jan-Today)	253	565
Total	4.4K	9.97K

Figure 7: Website Analytics - Summary

Figure 7 summarizes visitor and view statistics over different time frames. Cumulatively, the website recorded 4.4K visitors and 9.97K views. Regular monthly engagement is noted, with observable spikes coinciding with key project events and dissemination activities, reflecting the effectiveness of communication efforts during these periods. Notably, increased traffic aligns with periods surrounding plenary meetings and participation in major events (e.g., Code BEAM Europe, Hardwear.io, etc.) indicating that targeted communication around these milestones successfully drove audience engagement.

2.2 Social Media Engagement

Social media platforms play a key role in RESCALE's dissemination and communication strategy, enabling the consortium to reach a broader audience, foster engagement and provide timely updates on project activities. Social media channels offer an effective means to communicate with the scientific community, industry stakeholders, and the general public, amplifying the visibility of project outcomes.

These activities are guided by the social media strategy outlined in the dissemination and communication plan, which defines target metrics, posting frequency, and engagement practices to maximize reach and alignment with WP6 objectives.

Throughout the first 18 months, the RESCALE consortium actively utilized various social media platforms, including LinkedIn, Twitter/X and Facebook to share news, publications, events and project milestones. These platforms promote the project's objectives, highlight partner contributions and disseminate relevant information to followers and external stakeholders.

2.2.1 Twitter/X

Twitter/X offers a fast-paced platform ideal for real-time engagement and wide visibility. Its dynamic nature allows RESCALE to share immediate updates, amplify project visibility and participate in ongoing discussions relevant to cybersecurity and supply chain security.

The RESCALE project maintains an active presence on Twitter/X through its official account [RESCALE Project Horizon EU](#). The account operates under the handle [@RESCALE_EU](#) and serves as an essential communication channel for sharing timely updates, promoting events and engaging with stakeholders. Twitter/X enables the consortium to connect directly with the cybersecurity, supply chain and wider research communities, ensuring broad dissemination of project activities.

During the first 18 months of the project, the RESCALE Twitter/X account has steadily grown its audience. A total of 50 followers were gained during the first year, followed by an additional 19 followers in the second year to date, bringing the total follower count to 69.

The Twitter account has been consistently used to announce major project milestones, promote dissemination materials and foster engagement with the broader community. The published content includes:

- Project deliverables and key technical updates.
- Announcements regarding participation in conferences, workshops and public events.
- Various dissemination materials created.
- Collaborations and interactions with other related projects.
- Information about the consortium.
- Publications in journals and conferences.
- Supply chain security important news.

During the reporting period, a total of 101 tweets were published, covering these topics. The consortium will continue to utilize Twitter/X as a key dissemination tool, with a particular focus on increasing RESCALE's followers on Twitter/X through interaction with related Horizon Europe projects, research networks and industry bodies, ensuring RESCALE's results remain visible and accessible throughout the project lifecycle.

2.2.2 LinkedIn

The RESCALE project actively utilizes LinkedIn as one of its primary professional dissemination channels. Given LinkedIn's prominence in connecting with industry leaders, policymakers and researchers, it serves as a vital platform to strengthen RESCALE's outreach and stakeholder engagement.

The project's official LinkedIn page has been consistently maintained throughout the first 18 months, ensuring the visibility of RESCALE's key developments and progress. The project's official LinkedIn page is [RESCALE Project Horizon EU](#) and serves as a centralized hub for sharing updates and engaging with the professional community. Over the reporting period, the LinkedIn page has demonstrated continuous growth. By Month 18, it has accumulated 246 followers, with engagement steadily increasing as project outputs are published and shared. It gathered 180 followers during the first year and an additional 66 followers in the second year.

A total of 101 posts have been published on the page during the first 18 months, ensuring continuous engagement with the platform. Posts typically offer more detailed content than those shared on Twitter/X, focusing on promoting project milestones, technical achievements, consortium activities and participation in public events and collaborations. LinkedIn's professional nature has allowed the project to specifically target audiences relevant to the cybersecurity and supply chain sectors, fostering meaningful engagement within these communities.

As part of the established dissemination strategy, the LinkedIn page has been used to:

- Disseminate updates on submitted deliverables, publications and technical results.
- Share announcements regarding plenary meetings, workshop and participation in international conferences.
- Foster interactions with related Horizon Europe projects, research initiatives and stakeholder networks.

The effectiveness of LinkedIn as a dissemination tool has been continuously monitored using platform analytics. Metrics such as post impressions, members reached, clicks on shared content, reactions to posts and engagement rate are analyzed below for the period spanning from March 21 2024, to March 20 2025, which corresponds to the timeframe retained by LinkedIn analytics. Its important to note that the analytics for all metrics are presented for the period mentioned above and not for the whole reporting period, M1 to M18 because that is the data LinkedIn retains.

Figure 8: LinkedIn Analytics - Post Impressions

Figure 8 illustrates the total number of post impressions over the retained period, showing clear spikes in impressions during periods when key deliverables, events or publications were promoted. Notably, there was a significant spike around September 2024, aligning with major outreach efforts, such as attended events by the project. Over the analyzed period, RESCALE’s LinkedIn posts achieved a total of 22,869 organic impressions, with 0 sponsored impressions, indicating that all engagement was generated without paid promotion.

Figure 9: LinkedIn Analytics - Members Reached

Similarly, Figure 9 presents the total number of members reached over the analyzed period. The

chart demonstrates steady growth in audience engagement, with noticeable peaks corresponding to key dissemination periods. A significant increase is evident around September 2024, as with the previous metric.

In total, RESCALE’s LinkedIn posts reached 9,963 unique members organically, with no sponsored reach recorded during this timeframe.

Figure 10: LinkedIn Analytics - Clicks on Shared Content

Figure 10 shows the total number of clicks on shared content, reflecting audience interest in accessing detailed information and external resources. A noticeable increase is observed around November 2024 and January 2025, corresponding to specific posts.

Overall, the posts recorded a total of 1,872 organic clicks, with no clicks generated from sponsored content.

Figure 11: LinkedIn Analytics - Reactions

Figure 11 illustrates the total number of reactions (likes, comments, shares) received on posts throughout the analyzed period. The data indicates a steady accumulation of positive engagement, with clear spikes in reactions during months of increased dissemination activities such as September 2024 and January 2025.

In total, the posts generated 1,441 organic reactions, with no reactions coming from sponsored content, underscoring consistent, unpaid engagement.

Figure 12: LinkedIn Analytics - Engagement Rate

Lastly, Figure 12 depicts the engagement rate over the analyzed period. The engagement rate reflects the percentage of people who interacted with the content (via likes, comments, shares or clicks) relative to the total number of impressions. The chart shows consistent engagement levels, with noticeable peaks aligning with increased dissemination activities.

Throughout the period, RESCALE achieved an average organic engagement rate of 14.5%, with no engagement driven by sponsored content. This consistently high rate demonstrates the effectiveness of LinkedIn in fostering meaningful interaction with the project's target professional communities.

Moving forward, the consortium will continue to employ LinkedIn strategically to maximize professional outreach and ensure that project outcomes are disseminated effectively to targeted communities.

2.2.3 Facebook

In addition to LinkedIn and Twitter/X, the RESCALE project maintains an official Facebook page named [Rescale Project](#) as part of its broader dissemination strategy. Although not part of the KPIs on the Grant Agreement, Facebook serves as an additional channel to reach a wider, more diverse audience, including the general public, non-technical stakeholders and smaller industry entities. While Facebook is not formally included in KPI reporting, engagement on the platform is monitored internally using the same methods applied to LinkedIn and Twitter/X to support ongoing evaluation of outreach effectiveness. Its informal nature complements the more professional tone of LinkedIn and the real-time communication style of Twitter/X, contributing to a well-rounded communication approach.

Throughout the reporting period, the Facebook page has been regularly updated with key project news, event announcements and dissemination materials. A total of 31 followers have been reached so far.

While Facebook is not the primary platform for engaging specialized stakeholders, it is essential to ensure broad accessibility to project updates and foster general public awareness. The consortium will continue maintaining the Facebook page to complement other social media efforts and support overall visibility objectives.

2.2.4 Social Media Posts

Across all social media platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter/X and Facebook) the RESCALE consortium maintained a consistent and structured posting schedule throughout the first 18 months. Posts were carefully curated to align with the project's dissemination objectives, ensuring regular updates on progress, activities and outcomes. The types of content shared included but are not limited to (these are only examples of posts made):

- Announcements of public deliverables and key technical results.
- Updates on project events, such as plenary meetings and external collaborations.
- Participation in conferences, workshops and webinars.

- Promotion of blog articles, newsletters and press releases.
- Highlights of partner contributions and relevant external initiatives.

The frequency of posts was adapted based on project milestones and dissemination needs, with increased activity during certain periods in order to boost KPI numbers.

Through this sustained social media presence, the consortium successfully fostered visibility and engagement, ensuring timely communication of RESCALE's achievements to both specialized and general audiences.

2.2.5 YouTube

RESCALE's YouTube channel serves as a dynamic platform to visually communicate the project's advancements. By leveraging video content, RESCALE aims to engage a diverse audience, offering them an immersive insight into the project's mission to enhance supply chain security. The channel features a variety of content, such as project overview, use cases, description of RESCALE components, all designed to elucidate complex concepts in an accessible manner. This audiovisual approach complements RESCALE's traditional dissemination materials and broadens its outreach by appealing to those who prefer visual learning formats.

The channel is accessible at [RESCALE Project YouTube Channel](#) and is also associated with the handle [@RescaleProject](#). The RESCALE YouTube channel currently has 5 public videos, 21 subscribers and a total of 110 views at the time of this report. These metrics reflect the initial outreach efforts of the project, with expectations for growth as dissemination activities continue. Furthermore, two private videos describing how each pilot integrates and utilizes RESCALE have been prepared; these will be made publicly available once the corresponding deliverable D5.3 is approved. All YouTube videos have been published during the second year of the project. This timing ensures that the content reflects the project's progress and highlights key technical advancements achieved to date. Below, a brief summary of each published video is provided.

- **RESCALE Overview:** This introductory video presents the RESCALE project's mission and its innovative approach to securing supply chains. It highlights how RESCALE leverages automation, AI-driven tools and cross-layer methodologies to enhance vulnerability assessments, audits and protection across hardware and software layers.
- **Securing the Software Supply Chain:** This video focuses on RESCALE's Static Code Analysis Module, illustrating how it detects software vulnerabilities early in the development lifecycle. It demonstrates how static analysis integrates into CI/CD pipelines to automate security checks and generate detailed component assessments, serving as a critical first defense in modern software development practices.
- **Ensuring Software Security with RESCALE's Dynamic Testing Module:** The video showcases the Dynamic Testing Module, detailing how it complements static analysis by identifying vulnerabilities during live execution. Techniques such as fuzz testing are applied to uncover complex issues like buffer overflows and race conditions. The results are centralized in the DSCG, contributing to the overall TBOM.

- **Inside RESCALE's Static Analysis Toolkit:** This video provides an in-depth look at the core tools within RESCALE's Static Code Analysis Module. It explains how ML-based scanning, rule-based techniques and symbolic execution collectively detect a wide variety of software vulnerabilities. Special focus is given to how these tools reduce false positives and improve detection accuracy.
- **Unveiling Security Flaws in Low-Level Components:** This video highlights the Low-Level Security Testing Module, focusing on firmware, kernel and embedded software security. Tools like InSpectre Gadget, SafeFetch and FATex are presented, demonstrating how they detect critical vulnerabilities such as ROP gadget exploitation, speculative execution flaws and fault injection weaknesses. These findings feed into the DSCG to strengthen overall supply chain security.
- **Deployment of RESCALE in CC:** This private video presents how Chocolate Cloud utilizes RESCALE's tools and methodologies to enhance security within its pilot setup, demonstrating the practical application of RESCALE components.
- **Deployment of RESCALE in PST:** The second private video outlines the integration of RESCALE in the PST pilot environment, showing how the pilot employs RESCALE's solutions to improve supply chain security.

By maintaining an active YouTube presence, RESCALE ensures that its developments are effectively communicated to a broad audience, fostering greater understanding and engagement with the project. Posts are also made on RESCALE's social media channels further increasing visibility.

2.3 Digital Promotional Materials

This section presents the various digital promotional materials developed to support RESCALE's dissemination strategy. It includes a range of resources, such as newsletters, posters, flyers, brochures and articles designed to effectively communicate various aspects of the project to a broad audience. Each material is tailored to enhance visibility, foster stakeholder engagement and ensure alignment with the project's communication goals.

2.3.1 Newsletters

Newsletters are an integral component of the RESCALE dissemination strategy, designed to provide periodic, digestible updates on project progress, achievements and ongoing activities. They serve as a key communication component, ensuring that stakeholders, including industry partners, academic institutions, policymakers and the general public, remain informed and engaged throughout the project's lifecycle.

By presenting highlights in an accessible and visually appealing format, newsletters complement the more technical deliverables and publications, supporting broader visibility and outreach. Their distribution across multiple platforms ensures that RESCALE's objectives and results are communicated consistently to a wide audience. RESCALE also offers a newsletter

subscription form on the project website on the main page. Through this form, users can enter their email addresses to receive future editions of the newsletter directly in their inbox, ensuring timely and direct access to project updates, results and announcements.

During the first 18 months of the project, four editions of the RESCALE newsletter were developed and disseminated. Three issues were published during the first year, with one additional issue released in the second year to date. The newsletters are organized into volumes, with each volume corresponding to one project year. Each volume consists of three issues, ensuring regular updates throughout the year. All newsletters are made publicly available on the RESCALE Zenodo community [18], ensuring compliance with open-access requirements and providing a reliable, long-term repository for easy reference and citation. Newsletter issues are described in detail below:

- **RESCALE Newsletter Vol.1 Issue 1:** The first issue, released in January 2024, introduced the RESCALE project, its vision, objectives and the importance of secure-by-design supply chains. It provided an overview of initial activities, including the kick-off meeting, pilot use cases, KPIs and partner highlights. The issue also featured an analysis of cybersecurity market trends affecting the supply chain landscape and issues encountered in modern supply chains.
- **RESCALE Newsletter Vol.1 Issue 2:** The second issue, released in May 2024, offered insights into the RESCALE architecture design process along with the components comprising the architecture. It also covered the project's second plenary meeting hosted in Limassol, Cyprus.
- **RESCALE Newsletter Vol.1 Issue 3:** The third issue of the first volume, created in September 2024, highlighted technical achievements, including the presentation of the project's first complete architecture. It provided an overview of tools in RESCALE and covered the release of the project's first YouTube video. Additionally, it summarized the project's submitted deliverables, listed key publications, reported on collaborations with other projects and detailed participation in major events.
- **RESCALE Newsletter Vol.2 Issue 1:** The first issue of the second volume, released in March 2025, focuses on the tools developed within RESCALE for the Static Analysis Module and Dynamic Testing Module. It also presents key updates and milestones achieved following the completion of Year 1.

To maximize visibility, all newsletters were made available on the RESCALE project website through links directing to Zenodo. Specifically, the first three newsletters uploaded to Zenodo each received approximately 80 views, with the first issue reaching 70 downloads and the subsequent two achieving around 60 downloads each. The fourth newsletter was recently published on Zenodo, and as such, its view and download metrics are still accumulating, however its expected to reach the same numbers if not higher. Dissemination was further reinforced through promotion across the project's social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook), ensuring wide reach among various stakeholder groups.

2.3.2 Posters

Visual dissemination materials such as posters and roll-up banners are an essential part of RESCALE's communication toolkit. These materials are designed to convey concise, visually engaging summaries of the project's objectives, methodologies, use cases, innovations to diverse audiences during conferences, exhibitions, workshops and networking events.

By presenting key highlights in an accessible format, posters and banners complement detailed deliverables and publications produced by the project, supporting broader visibility and outreach. Their distribution across physical events and online platforms ensures that RESCALE's objectives and results are effectively communicated to a wide audience. During the first 18 months of the project, two major visual materials were developed to support dissemination efforts. Specifically, a project poster was released during the first year, followed by a roll-up banner in the second year. For reporting purposes, roll-up banners are considered equivalent to posters, as they serve the same dissemination function. Both materials have been uploaded to the RESCALE Zenodo community. The details of both materials are presented below.

- **RESCALE Poster:** The RESCALE poster provides high-level overview of the project's key goals, objectives and expected outcomes. It emphasizes RESCALE's mission to enhance supply chain security, highlighting core concepts such as Trusted Bill of Materials (TBOM) and the secure auditing of software and hardware components. Moreover, the poster presents the two complementary use cases, PST's cloud-edge deployment platform and SkyFlok's privacy-by-design distributed storage solution, demonstrating the project's applicability across diverse supply chain scenarios.
- **RESCALE Roll-Up Banner:** The roll-up banner complements the poster by also offering a visually impactful summary of RESCALE's objectives. It includes clear references to the project's use cases, consortium and dissemination channels, serving as a prominent visual tool for physical events.

Both the poster and roll-up banner are reviewed and updated as the project progresses and are made publicly accessible via the RESCALE project website through links directing to Zenodo. Posts are also shared across RESCALE's social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook), increasing visibility. Both materials have been actively used by consortium partners at various events, such as Code BEAM Europe 2024, Hardwear.io 2024 Netherlands and the CyberHOT Summer School 2024. The roll-up banner is primarily used at physical events to ensure a strong visual presence, while the poster is more frequently utilized at virtual events.

2.3.3 Flyers/Brochures

Printed and digital promotional materials such as flyers and brochures play a crucial role in RESCALE's dissemination strategy. These materials are particularly useful during both virtual and physical events, where they provide attendees with a concise yet informative snapshot of the project's scope and progress. A typical RESCALE flyer or brochure includes key elements such as the project's overview, objectives, technical approach, consortium partners, use cases and contact information, offering stakeholders an accessible overview without requiring in-depth prior knowledge. For reporting purposes, leaflets are considered equivalent to flyers, as

they serve the same dissemination function. Flyers, leaflets and brochures are made publicly available through the RESCALE Zenodo community. During the first 18 months, the following promotional material was developed:

- **RESCALE Leaflet:** A comprehensive leaflet was developed to summarize RESCALE's overarching vision, core objectives and concepts. It highlights key focus areas, including secure-by-design supply chains, AI-enhanced protection mechanisms and in-depth code auditing. The leaflet also presents the consortium partners and basic information about the project, such as the duration of the project, how many countries are involved, etc. The leaflet has been actively utilized at public events, and serves to reinforce RESCALE's branding and to provide a clear overview of the project's mission.
- **RESCALE Flyer:** The RESCALE flyer presents similar information to the leaflet, including the project's objectives, key capabilities and overall mission, but in a different visual format. It also includes the two project use cases and a graphical presentation of RESCALE's initial architecture.

Both the leaflet and flyer are publicly accessible through the RESCALE project website via links directing to the RESCALE Zenodo community. These materials have been used for dissemination at various events that the consortium participated in representing RESCALE, including but not limited to Code BEAM Europe 2024, Hardwear.io 2024 Netherlands, and the CyberHOT Summer School 2024, etc.

2.3.4 Blog/Articles

In addition to traditional dissemination materials, RESCALE actively engages with its audience through insightful blog posts and articles. These writings explore various aspects of the project's progress, with a particular emphasis on its technical components, methodologies and tools. They provide detailed explanations of RESCALE's architecture, code testing modules and security mechanisms, offering readers an in-depth understanding of the project's contributions to supply chain security.

All articles are publicly available on the RESCALE project website. Recognizing the value of streamlined communication, RESCALE has consolidated its news and blog pages into a single unified [Blog/News](#) page, providing stakeholders with one central source for updates and insights. Below, a summary of each published article is presented.

- **Securing the Software Supply Chain: How RESCALE's Static Code Analysis Module Enhances Security:** This article explores the pivotal role of the Static Code Analysis Module within RESCALE, highlighting how it safeguards software supply chains by analyzing code for vulnerabilities and ensuring compliance with security standards. It emphasizes the importance of early detection of security flaws to maintain a secure software supply chain.
- **Inside RESCALE's Static Analysis Toolkit: SAVE-ME, SASTER, and IVEE:** This piece provides an in-depth look into the tools powering RESCALE's Static Code Analysis Module. It discusses how SAVE-ME leverages Machine Learning (ML) for vulnerability detection, SASTER-cli integrates multiple static code analysis tools before

applying ML, and IVEE utilizes symbolic execution to identify complex security issues, collectively enhancing the accuracy and depth of static analysis.

- **Ensuring Software Security with RESCALE's Dynamic Testing Module:** Focusing on the Dynamic Testing Module, this article addresses the necessity of dynamic testing in identifying vulnerabilities that manifest during runtime. It outlines how the module executes software in controlled environments to detect issues arising from interactions, input handling and real-world execution conditions, ensuring a comprehensive security evaluation before deployment.
- **The Tools Powering RESCALE's Dynamic Testing Module:** This article delves into the specific tools integrated within RESCALE's Dynamic Testing Module, such as RAISE and EvoMaster. It explains how each tool contributes to enhancing dynamic security analysis by focusing on aspects like fuzz testing, API security evaluation and behavioral analysis, thereby strengthening the overall security assessment process.
- **Strengthening Supply Chain Security: The Low-Level Security Testing Module in RESCALE:** This piece highlights the significance of assessing low-level system components, such as firmware and kernel modules in modern cybersecurity. It discusses how RESCALE's Low-Level Security Testing Module identifies vulnerabilities in these critical areas, ensuring comprehensive supply chain security by applying specialized testing techniques.
- **Unveiling Security Flaws in Low-Level Components: The Tools Behind RESCALE's Low-Level Security Testing Module:** This article examines the specialized tools integrated into RESCALE's Low-Level Security Testing Module, including InSpectre Gadget, SafeFetch and FATex. It explains how these tools systematically analyze firmware, detect execution flaws and assess security vulnerabilities in embedded and kernel-level components, providing automated methods for identifying low-level security weaknesses.
- **Detecting Hardware Vulnerabilities: The Role of RESCALE's Dynamic Hardware Analyzer:** This article explores the importance of hardware-level security and introduces RESCALE's Dynamic Hardware Analyzer. It explains how the module detects side-channel attack vulnerabilities, power analysis issues and data leakage risks in cryptographic and FPGA-based systems.
- **Analyzing Hardware Security: The Tools Powering RESCALE's Dynamic Hardware Analyzer:** This article presents the toolchain behind the Dynamic Hardware Analyzer, highlighting how FlexLECO, ChipWhisperer and on-chip sensors support precise trace collection, while software libraries enable preprocessing, statistical analysis and ML-driven attack simulations.

By maintaining an active blog page, RESCALE ensures continuous engagement with its stakeholders and the general public, providing transparency and insights into the project's ongoing developments and technical innovations.

This activity is directly aligned with the stakeholder engagement goals outlined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan, which designates the blog as a primary vehicle for translating technical results into accessible content. The Dissemination and Communication Plan sets a target of six blog articles per year, using these updates to foster visibility, encourage feedback and track engagement from stakeholders across research, industry and policy sectors.

3 Scientific and Technical Dissemination

Scientific and technical dissemination is a critical pillar of the RESCALE project's outreach strategy. Throughout the first 18 months of the project, the consortium has actively engaged in various dissemination activities to ensure that the project's results, methodologies and innovations are effectively disseminated to the academic community and industry stakeholders. These efforts support knowledge transfer, foster collaboration, and contribute to broader advancements in supply chain security and cybersecurity. This section presents an overview of the scientific and technical dissemination efforts undertaken during the reporting period, structured across the following key areas:

- Publications in peer-reviewed journals and conferences.
- Book chapters.
- Networking and outreach events.
- Collaboration with EU-funded projects.

3.1 Publications in Peer-reviewed Journals and Conferences

Publishing in peer-reviewed venues is the primary channel through which RESCALE disseminates its scientific findings. During the first reporting period (M1-M18), the consortium produced a total of 14 peer-reviewed publications, including 13 conference papers published in top tier conferences and one journal article. These publications reflect the consortium's focus on various aspects of supply chain security, some of which are summarized below:

- Low-level vulnerability detection, speculative execution attacks and hardware-level security (e.g., Spectre attacks, speculative race conditions, double-fetch protection, etc.).
- Secure software analysis methodologies, including context-sensitive fuzzing, static and dynamic analysis and memory safety.
- Supply chain security practices, with emphasis on SBOM/TBOM and vulnerability management within real-world systems.
- Privacy, monetization and trust models in supply chains, as well as malware detection and emerging attack vectors.
- Automation techniques for vulnerability classification (e.g., CWE assignment, etc.).
- Cryptographic performance and security optimization techniques in embedded and secure systems.

Table 1 presents all publications of this type made during the reporting period.

No.	Date	Type	Journal/Conference Name	Paper Link
1	29/02/2024	Conference	NDSS Symposium 2024	View Publication [2]
2	22/05/2024	Conference	45th IEEE Symposium on Security & Privacy	View Publication [7]
3	22/05/2024	Conference	45th IEEE Symposium on Security & Privacy	View Publication [6]
4	14/08/2024	Conference	33rd USENIX Security Symposium	View Publication [15]
5	14/08/2024	Conference	33rd USENIX Security Symposium	View Publication [5]
6	16/08/2024	Conference	33rd USENIX Security Symposium	View Publication [11]
7	30/06/2024	Conference	14th International Symposium on Business Modeling and Software Design	View Publication [17]
8	30/06/2024	Conference	14th International Symposium on Business Modeling and Software Design	View Publication [9]
9	30/06/2024	Conference	14th International Symposium on Business Modeling and Software Design	View Publication [16]
10	08/07/2024	Conference	DevSecOps Research and Opportunities 2024 Workshop, Co-located with the 9th IEEE European Symposium on Security and Privacy	View Publication [12]
11	08/07/2024	Conference	3rd Workshop on Rethinking Malware Analysis (WoRMA), Co-located with the 9th IEEE European Symposium on Security & Privacy	View Publication [8]
12	03/07/2024	Conference	SAMOS XXIV International Conference on Embedded Computer Systems: Architectures, Modeling and Simulation	View Publication [4]
13	28/10/2024	Conference	Cloud-Edge Continuum (CEC 2024) Workshop, Co-located with the 32nd IEEE International Conference on Network Protocols (ICNP 2024)	View Publication [1]
14	14/11/2024	Journal	The Computer Journal, 2024	View Publication [14]

Table 1: Publications in Conferences and Journals

All RESCALE publications are made publicly available through the RESCALE Zenodo community, ensuring transparency and alignment with Horizon Europe’s open science policy. Additionally, the publications are accessible via the project website, with direct links pointing to their corresponding Zenodo entries. To further enhance visibility and engagement, posts announcing each publication are shared across RESCALE’s social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook).

It is important to note that several publications (specifically, publications numbered 7 to 11 and 13 in Table 1) are currently under embargo. These will be uploaded to the RESCALE Zenodo community immediately following the conclusion of the embargo period, ensuring full open access to all scientific outputs. The embargo expiry dates are actively monitored and documented within the internal KPI tracking excel file (for more information about the

file check Subsection 4.1), ensuring timely and compliant uploads once the embargo period finishes.

3.2 Book Chapters

In addition to journal and conference publications, book chapters play a key role in disseminating RESCALE's findings to a broader academic and professional audience. Book chapters allow for comprehensive, in-depth exploration of specific topics and methodologies developed within the project, offering readers a cohesive understanding of how RESCALE's technologies contribute to advancing supply chain security. During the the first 18 months of the project, one book chapter was accepted for publication but has not yet been published. RESCALE's book chapter primarily focuses on supply chain security concepts, aligning closely with the project's core objectives.

The book chapter that RESCALE contributed is titled **“Securing the Software Supply Chain: Innovations and Approaches”** in the **“Holistic IoT Security, Privacy and Safety: Integrated Approaches Protecting A Highly Connected World”** book, which is published by **“Now Publishers”**. The chapter focuses on supply chain security concepts. The book is scheduled for publication in 2025.

The book chapter will be made publicly accessible and supports RESCALE's commitment to open access and wide dissemination, ensuring that its insights reach academic, industrial and policy-making communities alike.

3.3 Networking and Outreach events

Networking and outreach activities are central to RESCALE's mission of fostering engagement with industry, academia, policymakers and the wider cybersecurity community. Throughout the first 18 months, the consortium actively participated in a range of events to promote the project, establish new collaborations and disseminate results. Table 2 provides an overview of all events attended by the RESCALE consortium during the reporting period. These events were selected based on their strategic alignment with RESCALE's objectives, particularly their focus on cybersecurity, hardware security and secure software development. Priority was given to events that attract key stakeholders across industry, academia and policy, offering opportunities for technical exchange and contribution to policy dialogue. Detailed information about each event is presented in the corresponding subsections, categorized by event type.

No.	Date	Type	Event Name
1	03/11/2023	Industry Exhibitions/summits	Hardwear.io 2023 Netherlands
2	23/01/2024	EU Networking events	6Gsec Common Path and Cardinal Points (6Gsec CP ²) 2024
3	19/03/2024	EU Networking events	DFRWS EU 2024 Zaragoza
4	28/03/2024	Industry Exhibitions/summits	World Cybersecurity Summit 2024
5	30/07/2024	EU Networking events	International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions (IWAPS) 2024
6	14/10/2024	Industry Exhibitions/summits	Code BEAM Europe 2024
7	23/10/2024	Industry Exhibitions/summits	Hardwear.io 2024 Netherlands

Table 2: Events the Consortium Participated In

3.3.1 Industry Exhibition and Summits

Participation in industry exhibitions and summits is an essential component of RESCALE's dissemination strategy in terms of attended events. These events provide valuable opportunities to engage directly with cybersecurity professionals, hardware and software developers and industry leaders. By participating in such exhibitions, the project ensures visibility within key communities, fosters networking and collaboration and promotes awareness of RESCALE's objectives, technological advancements and results. The following exhibitions and summits were attended by consortium partners during the first 18 months of the project:

- **Hardwear.io 2023 Netherlands:** The Hardwear.io 2023 conference in the Netherlands is a prominent industry event focused on hardware security. It features intensive training sessions, keynote talks, workshops and hands-on activities such as Capture-the-Flag competitions, all led by industry experts. RESCALE was represented there by the consortium, whose attendance aimed at maintaining project visibility and engagement with the hardware security community. The event allowed the consortium to establish valuable connections and promote awareness of RESCALE's objectives.
- **World Cybersecurity Summit 2024:** The World Cybersecurity Summit 2024 brought together leading experts, policymakers and technology companies to discuss emerging challenges in the cybersecurity domain. Key topics included advancements in AI-driven security, strategies for enhancing resilience in the digital ecosystem and approaches to counteract evolving cyber threats. The consortium participated in the event to promote RESCALE's objectives and ensure project visibility. Project partners delivered a presentation that included slides highlighting the RESCALE project and its relevance to current cybersecurity trends.
- **Code BEAM Europe 2024:** Code BEAM Europe 2024 is an industry summit focusing on Erlang, Elixir and BEAM technologies. It consists of two days of technical talks, workshops and discussions dedicated to high-performance, fault-tolerant software systems. The consortium attended the event, ensuring RESCALE's presence within the developer community and promoting the project's relevance to functional programming

environments. The consortium hosted a booth and actively disseminated RESCALE materials, including flyers and brochures. Furthermore, presentations delivered at the event highlighted RESCALE's contributions to secure software deployment and supply chain security.

- **Hardware.io 2024 Netherlands:** Building on the previous year's engagement, the consortium participated once again in Hardware.io 2024 in the Netherlands. This edition introduced new workshops and advanced training sessions focused on emerging challenges in hardware security. The consortium disseminated RESCALE promotional materials, such as posters and leaflets to inform participants about the project's scope and technological innovations. The event provided expanded networking opportunities with hardware security experts, reinforcing RESCALE's presence in this critical domain.

3.3.2 EU Networking Events

Participation in EU networking events is another key aspect of RESCALE's dissemination strategy in terms of attended events. It enables the project to engage with relevant stakeholders, align with European research priorities and foster collaboration with other initiatives. Below the EU networking events attended by the consortium are presented:

- **6Gsec Common Path and Cardinal Points (6Gsec CP²):** The 6Gsec CP² event brought together experts and stakeholders from the cybersecurity and telecommunications sectors to discuss emerging challenges and policies related to 6G networks. The event emphasized threat landscapes, research agendas and collaborative opportunities within the evolving digital ecosystem. The consortium represented RESCALE, delivering a few slides that included a project overview and key objectives. No dissemination materials were distributed during this event.
- **DFRWS EU 2024 Zaragoza:** The DFRWS EU 2024 conference focused on advancements in digital forensics, covering topics such as mobile forensics, AI applications and emerging investigation techniques. The hybrid event featured keynotes, workshops and presentations from leading researchers and practitioners in the field. The consortium attended the conference, ensuring visibility of RESCALE within the digital forensics community. No dissemination materials were presented during this attendance.
- **International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions (IWAPS) 2024:** The 4th International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions (IWAPS) was held in conjunction with the ARES conference. The workshop focused on advancements in privacy and security technologies, covering algorithms, protocols and trust frameworks relevant to next-generation architectures. RESCALE co-organized the event alongside other Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects. This co-organization marked a key dissemination achievement, significantly boosting the project's visibility within the privacy-preserving research community. RESCALE was featured in the workshop's promotional materials and official website and engaged directly with attendees from academia and industry, reinforcing the project's role in shaping the ongoing dialogue on privacy-enhancing technologies.

These networking activities not only enhanced awareness of RESCALE's contributions but also provided valuable opportunities for establishing relationships with key players in the cybersecurity and supply chain sectors. Such engagements are essential for supporting the long-term adoption and sustainability of RESCALE's solutions.

3.3.3 Consortium-led Events

In addition to participating in external conferences and networking events, RESCALE has contributed to the wider cybersecurity community by organizing or co-organizing hands-on training events and demonstrations. These events serve as important platforms for knowledge transfer, skill development and stakeholder engagement, offering direct interaction with ICT practitioners, researchers and students.

- **Cybersecurity Hands-On Training (CyberHOT) Summer School 2024:** The 4th CyberHOT Summer School was organized by 1 partner from the consortium with an additional partner participating. This event provided practical cybersecurity training tailored to ICT professionals, technical managers, system administrators, penetration testers, ethical hackers, software developers and students. RESCALE's involvement in organizing CyberHOT strengthened the project's outreach and educational impact within the cybersecurity community. While no specific dissemination materials were presented, RESCALE's visibility was reinforced through active engagement in the sessions. CyberHOT is planned as an annual event, and RESCALE will continue to participate each year, reinforcing the project's ongoing commitment to hands-on cybersecurity education and community engagement.

3.4 Collaboration with EU-funded Projects

Establishing synergies and collaborations with other EU-funded research initiatives is a key element of RESCALE's dissemination and impact strategy. These collaborations promote knowledge exchange and avoid duplication of efforts through shared objectives and complementary expertise.

During the first 18 months of the project, the RESCALE consortium initiated collaboration with the **SYNAPSE** Horizon Europe project, which focuses on enhancing the security and resilience of supply chains. Initial discussions identified strong alignment between RESCALE's secure-by-design supply chain approach and SYNAPSE's objectives.

An introductory meeting was organized, where representatives from both projects, including the project coordinators presented their respective visions, methodologies and overview of their projects. The meeting served as a platform for establishing mutual understanding and identifying potential areas of cooperation, particularly in:

- Sharing best practices for supply chain security solutions.
- Exploring interoperability between tools and frameworks.

- Coordinating dissemination efforts to maximize visibility and outreach.

Moving forward, the collaboration with SYNAPSE is expected to continue through joint dissemination activities.

3.5 Zenodo

Zenodo is a widely recognized open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program [10] and operated by CERN [3]. It provides researchers, projects and institutions with a secure, reliable platform for preserving and disseminating a wide range of research outputs. Its role in promoting transparency, long-term accessibility and compliance with open science policies makes it an essential tool for Horizon Europe projects, including RESCALE. Zenodo is identified as a key dissemination channel in the Dissemination and Communication Plan (for more information see Annex A), supporting the project's commitment to open access and stakeholder engagement.

RESCALE has established its own dedicated community on Zenodo, titled **RESCALE Project**. This community serves as the central repository for all publicly available outputs generated during the project's lifecycle. By consolidating all dissemination materials in one accessible platform, RESCALE ensures both compliance with Horizon Europe's open access requirements and ease of access for stakeholders and the broader public.

The RESCALE Zenodo community features a dedicated curation policy, ensuring that all uploaded materials align with the project's objectives and quality standards. The community page also includes an overview of the project, displays the official RESCALE logo, provides a direct link to the project website and lists some of the organizations involved in the consortium to offer clear context to all visitors. Key uploads to the RESCALE Zenodo community are described below.

- **Public deliverables:** All non-confidential project deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo to ensure transparency and open access in line with Horizon Europe requirements. Deliverables are uploaded to the RESCALE Zenodo community only after their approval by the European Commission. As of now, one deliverable has been uploaded, corresponding to the single deliverable approved during the reporting period.
- **Scientific publications:** Published journal articles, conference papers and book chapters are uploaded to Zenodo when permitted by publisher policies. This practice maximizes the visibility, accessibility and long-term preservation of RESCALE's scientific contributions, ensuring that they can be freely accessed and cited by the research community and the public. Certain publications may be subject to embargo periods imposed by publishers. In such cases, the respective publications are uploaded to the RESCALE Zenodo community immediately after the embargo period concludes, maintaining the project's commitment to open access and knowledge dissemination. To date, 9 out of 14 publications have been uploaded to the community, with the remaining 5 publications currently under embargo.
- **Dissemination material:** All dissemination material, including each edition of the RESCALE newsletter, project flyers, brochures, posters, and related promotional content, are up-

loaded to Zenodo. This ensures stakeholders have consistent, centralized access to official, up-to-date information about the project's objectives, progress, events and key achievements. Making these materials openly available supports wide visibility, reinforces project branding and enables effective communication across diverse channels. All dissemination materials produced so far have been uploaded to Zenodo without restrictions.

As of the end of the first reporting period, the RESCALE Zenodo community recorded 1050 views and 813 downloads across all uploaded materials. In the second year, the community has continued to attract interest, with the number of views and downloads steadily increasing. These metrics reflect the effectiveness of the platform in disseminating RESCALE's outputs and engaging stakeholders.

Through regular uploads to the RESCALE Zenodo community, RESCALE ensures that its outputs remain openly accessible, supporting knowledge transfer and maximizing project impact.

4 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Impact Assessment

This section provides an overview of the mechanisms used to monitor dissemination progress and evaluates the effectiveness of RESCALE's outreach efforts through measurable indicators. By tracking key performance metrics, the project can assess the visibility, reach and impact of its communication and dissemination activities. These KPIs were initially defined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan, and the Description of Action (DoA), ensuring alignment with project-level obligations and strategic goals. The following subsections outline how performance is monitored, present a summary of relevant KPIs and evaluate their outcomes in the context of the project's objectives.

4.1 Monitoring Mechanisms

To systematically track progress and performance across all dissemination activities, the RESCALE project utilizes an internal KPI monitoring Excel file. This file is maintained by the Dissemination Manager and is updated on a monthly basis at the end of each month. It plays a central role in documenting all KPIs and ensuring alignment with the communication objectives defined under WP6. The monitoring file is structured into multiple dedicated sheets, each focusing on a specific area:

- **Dissemination - KPIs:** Tracks the overall dissemination KPIs, including followers on social media platforms, number of publications, promotional material, newsletters, etc.
- **WP6 - KPIs:** Captures the specific KPIs defined for WP6 in the project's DoA, supporting high-level progress evaluation. This subset also helps assess strategic alignment with RESCALE's intended impact pathways, ensuring that dissemination activities contribute meaningfully to the project's expected outcomes as outlined in the DoA and Dissemination and Communication Plan.
- **Publications:** Logs all published or submitted scientific outputs, including conferences, journals and book chapters, with information about publication date, venue, publisher, ISSN/ISBN, author from the project, paper link and embargo status.
- **Events:** Documents participation in or organization of events across all types (e.g., summits, EU networking events, workshops, etc), with specific details such as event date, who from the consortium attends or organizes it, and additional information on what materials are used, if there is a booth or not, etc.
- **Project Synergies:** Tracks collaborative dissemination activities with other Horizon Europe or Horizon 2020 projects.
- **Social Media Rotation:** Schedules and manages the rotation of post responsibilities among partners to ensure consistent presence on LinkedIn, Twitter/X and Facebook.

This comprehensive tracking mechanism supports several critical functions. It ensures internal transparency, enabling all consortium members to monitor dissemination progress. It facilitates evidence-based reporting, providing reliable input for deliverables and periodic reviews. By enabling adaptive dissemination, the consortium can refine its strategy in response to emerging needs and feedback. It also supports centralized coordination, helping ensure that all activities remain aligned with project-level messaging and branding. Finally, it contributes to audit readiness, offering structured records to support project evaluations and external audits.

The monitoring file is securely stored under the following path in the RESCALE repository, “**RESCALE Project Repository – WP6 – Documents Additional Technical Material – RESCALE WP6 - KPIs, dissemination and publications register.xlsx**”.

Selected data from this internal KPI tracking file is summarized and visualized in Section 4.2 supporting the quantitative analysis of dissemination impact during the first 18 months of the project.

4.2 Summary of KPIs Related to Dissemination

To provide a clear and quantifiable overview of dissemination progress, this subsection presents the specific KPIs defined for the RESCALE project. These include both annual targets and cumulative goals spanning the full project duration. The KPIs cover a wide range of dissemination categories, such as website traffic, social media activity, scientific publications, promotional outputs, event participation and inter-project collaboration. By reporting exact figures against set targets, the tables below offer an evidence-based assessment of RESCALE’s performance and highlight areas for strategic adjustment where needed.

Table 3 presents the annual dissemination KPIs, showcasing RESCALE’s performance across Year 1 and partially across Year 2 (since we are currently in Month 18). Each KPI includes a short description, the target that needs to be reached which is the same for all 3 years of the project, current number for both year 1 and 2 offering a clear snapshot of ongoing efforts and areas requiring additional focus.

Activities/Measures	Description	Target KPI	Y1	Y2
Project Website	≥ 1,000 users annually; ≥ 90 sec average engagement time	1000	3833	567
Zenodo Community	≥ 1,000 views annually	1000	1010	40
Zenodo Community	≥ 150 downloads annually (deliverables, publications, materials, e.g presentations)	150	459	354
Social Media	≥ 100 new followers annually in Twitter	100	50	19
Social Media	≥ 100 new followers annually in LinkedIn	100	180	66
Social Media	≥ 15 posts monthly in Twitter and LinkedIn	15	15	3.2
Social Media	≥ 4 videos annually in YouTube	4	4	3
Blogs/Articles	≥ 6 target blogs/ articles annually	6	6	2
Newsletters	≥ 3 newsletters annually	3	3	1

Table 3: Annual Dissemination KPIs

In addition to annual tracking, RESCALE monitors its overall dissemination goals for the entire

project duration. Table 4 presents the cumulative KPIs over the full 36-month period, allowing the consortium to assess long-term progress and strategic alignment.

Activities/Measures	Description	Target KPI	Y1-Y3
Journal publications	≥ 8 peer-reviewed publications	8	1
Int. Conferences	≥ 20 peer-reviewed publications	20	13
Special issues	≥ 5 special issues/book chapters/-magazine articles	5	1
Workshops/Field tests	≥ 2 workshops/special sessions; ≥ 40 attendees	2	0
EU-focused events	≥ 2 demonstrations (MVP and complete solutions)	2	0
Technical, Academic, Industrial events	≥ 6 demonstrations/ webinars/ training events	6	1
Interactive face-to-face networking	≥ 3 EU Networking Events	3	3
Interactive face-to-face networking	≥ 3 consortium led Info days	3	1
Interactive face-to-face networking	≥ 3 Industry Exhibitions/summits	3	3
Collaboration with other projects & initiatives	≥ 3 synergies established with Horizon Projects	3	1
Collaboration with other projects & initiatives	≥ 3 synergies established with other pertinent initiatives	3	0
Collaboration with Policy Makers and Standardization bodies	≥ 1 meeting with industry stakeholders per country represented in the consortium	11	0
Collaboration with Policy Makers and Standardization bodies	≥ 2 meetings with cybersecurity policy makers at national and EU level	2	0
Social Media	≥ 500 total views of YouTube content	500	110
Presentations	≥ 6 flyers/brochures	6	2
Presentations	≥ 3 posters	3	2
Presentations	≥ 9 audience specific project presentations	9	0
Traditional Media	≥ 1 articles/interviews to national magazines and/or newspapers per country represented by the consortium partners	1	0

Table 4: KPIs Covering Entire Project Period (Y1-Y3)

Together, these KPIs serve not only as accountability metrics but also as planning tools, helping the consortium adjust dissemination strategies to maximize impact, address underperforming areas, and capitalize on successful outreach channels. They also contribute directly to periodic internal reviews and external reporting obligations under Horizon Europe.

4.3 Assessment of Dissemination Effectiveness

During the first reporting period (M1-M18), the RESCALE project has made substantial progress across several dissemination and communication KPIs, with notable successes in areas such as

scientific publications, website engagement and promotional material development. At the same time, certain indicators remain underachieved or at a nascent stage, requiring increased focus in the upcoming project phases to ensure alignment with the overall dissemination strategy and Horizon Europe impact expectations.

A major achievement lies in the scientific dissemination domain. RESCALE has already exceeded its annual target for peer-reviewed publications, producing a total of 14 publications (13 conference papers and 1 journal article). Similarly, the project has already published 1 book chapter. This performance reflects the consortium's strong commitment to academic excellence and to sharing the project's technical contributions with the broader research community.

The website metrics also demonstrate effective outreach. The project's website recorded approximately 3,900 unique visitors in total for year 1, far surpassing the annual KPI of 1,000 users. Furthermore, the average engagement time per user exceeds 90 seconds, validating the relevance and usability of the website's content. Likewise, Zenodo view and download statistics significantly outpace their respective targets, with 1010 views and 459 downloads recorded in Year 1, exceeding the annual targets of 1,000 views and 150 downloads respectively. These figures indicate effective visibility and accessibility of RESCALE's outputs to external audiences.

Furthermore, the number of developed promotional materials (e.g., flyers, leaflets, posters, etc.) met the expected threshold, further supporting stakeholder engagement efforts. RESCALE also significantly outperformed the annual KPI for LinkedIn, gaining 180 followers in Year 1 alone, nearly doubling the expected yearly target and reflecting strong initial engagement with the professional community. It also has gained another 66 followers up to this point well on its way to achieving the annual KPI.

However, some KPIs require further improvement to meet their cumulative targets. Notably, the number of Twitter/X followers has yet to reach the expected annual target of 100 new followers per platform. Specifically, RESCALE gained 65 followers in Year 1, suggesting lackluster progress, but Twitter/X engagement remains modest with 50 followers in Year 1 and only 18 additional followers in Year 2. This falls short of the annual KPI and highlights the need for more consistent cross-platform promotion, inter-project tagging and coordinated campaigns in the second reporting period.

Similarly, the YouTube channel is currently below target, with 21 subscribers and only 110 total views. Although the project has successfully produced 5 public videos, meeting the KPI for video content development, subscriber growth remains limited. This under performance may be attributed to the delayed timing of video releases. Improved video dissemination and promotion, such as embedding videos in newsletters and blog posts will be prioritized to drive platform engagement.

In the area of event participation, the consortium has made considerable progress, participating in 7 events over the first 18 months. RESCALE has also organized 1 event (CyberHOT Summer School) so far.

It is also important to note that several KPIs, particularly those related to MVP demonstrations, workshops, meetings with industry stakeholders and cybersecurity policy makers, articles/interviews to national magazines or newspapers, remain at 0 as of M18. This is expected, as these activities are scheduled to follow after the development of the RESCALE MVP, which will serve as the primary foundation for demonstration and coordinated outreach. The activi-

ties surrounding these KPIs are planned the second half of the project (M19-M36) and will be activated as soon as the MVP is finalized.

Moreover, project collaboration KPIs require increased attention. Going forward, the project will intensify coordination with related Horizon Europe initiatives and non-Horizon Europe initiatives.

In summary, the first reporting period demonstrates that RESCALE has successfully achieved or surpassed multiple key KPIs, particularly in scientific dissemination, website traffic and promotional material production. For the remaining KPIs, especially those under-performing in Year 1, such as Twitter engagement, YouTube views, concrete actions have been planned to intensify engagement during Year 2 and Year 3. These targeted improvements will ensure that the dissemination and communication strategy continues to evolve in a results-driven and impactful manner, contributing to the overall success of the project.

4.4 Alignment with the Dissemination and Communication Plan and Deviations

The dissemination and communication activities conducted during the first 18 months of the RESCALE project have largely followed the structure and priorities outlined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) which is included in Annex A of this deliverable. The plan served as the central guiding document, defining stakeholder groups, communication channels and monitoring tools. This subsection outlines how the actual implementation aligns with the DCP, while also acknowledging minor deviations and adaptations that were necessary during execution.

4.4.1 Alignment with the DCP

Several aspects of the dissemination strategy have remained fully consistent with the DCP:

- **Stakeholder Mapping:** The project's outreach activities have targeted all core stakeholder groups identified in the DCP, including industry, academia, policymakers and the general public.
- **KPI Monitoring:** As planned, dissemination KPIs were tracked continuously using structured Excel monitoring files (described in the DCP and Deliverable Subsection 4.1).
- **Social Media Strategy:** The rotation plan for social media post contributions and the use of hashtags, tagging and visual content, as defined in the DCP, was followed in practice.
- **Channel Usage:** All primary channels described in the DCP, LinkedIn, Twitter/X, Facebook, the website, YouTube and Zenodo, were fully established and actively used as foreseen.
- **Content Formats and Frequency:** The production and dissemination of newsletters, flyers, posters, blog articles has also been followed as per the scheduling defined in the DCP.

4.4.2 Identified Deviations

While the core structure of the DCP has been maintained, certain deviations were required due to project dynamics:

- **Social Media Growth:** While the DCP outlines ambitious follower growth and content frequency across platforms, Twitter/X engagement has been slower than anticipated. As a result, the consortium has adapted by prioritizing LinkedIn and shifting focus there. Mitigation measures are also described in this report in regards to the slow Twitter growth.
- **Delayed Press and Media Engagement:** Traditional media coverage (e.g., national interviews, etc.) was originally scheduled to begin earlier. However, this was postponed to align with the MVP timeline, ensuring more concrete outcomes are available for press engagement.
- **Postponed Demonstrations and Events:** Several important activities (e.g., workshops and field tests, MVP demonstrations, stakeholder meetings) remain at zero. This is not a failure to follow the plan, but these activities will be performed during the second reporting period, after MVP development. This is acknowledged in Section 4.3 of this deliverable.
- **YouTube Content Timing:** While the DCP specified quarterly video releases, all public videos were clustered in the second project year. The consortium opted to delay publishing until technical content was mature enough to ensure value and engagement.

5 Conclusions & Future Steps

This deliverable provides a strategic overview of the dissemination and communication efforts carried out during the first half of the RESCALE project, corresponding to Months 1 through 18. It serves as both a record of dissemination achievements to date and a strategic guide for refining and scaling outreach activities in the second half of the project.

Across this period, dissemination has been closely aligned with RESCALE's broader objectives, ensuring the visibility of technical results, strengthening stakeholder outreach and maintaining compliance with open access and Horizon Europe communication obligations. The consortium employed a multi-pronged approach, leveraging digital channels, scientific publishing, physical and online events, and project synergies to reach both specialized and general audiences.

The sections that follow highlight key operational and strategic challenges encountered during this phase, summarize the overall effectiveness of dissemination activities and outline the planned actions that will guide communication and outreach efforts in the second half of the project.

5.1 Challenges & Lessons Learned

The first reporting period of the RESCALE project has provided valuable insights into the complexities of executing a comprehensive and multi-layered dissemination strategy across diverse audiences and channels. Several challenges emerged during this phase, offering important lessons that will guide the refinement of future dissemination efforts:

- **Early-stage Technical Abstraction:** One of the primary challenges was effectively communicating RESCALE's technical depth during the early stages of development, when several modules were still evolving. Translating complex, low-level research outputs (e.g., firmware vulnerability testing, speculative execution analysis, etc.) into engaging dissemination content required close coordination between technical and communication teams. To address this, WP6 was involved early in technical work package discussions, enabling clearer scoping of messaging needs and improving the quality and accuracy of communication outputs.
- **Ensuring Balanced Social Media Growth:** While the project saw solid engagement on LinkedIn, growing a consistent follower base on platforms like Twitter/X and Facebook proved more difficult. This highlights the need for tailored content strategies per platform, taking into account audience behavior and content type preferences. It also underscored the importance of cross-promotion between platforms to drive synergy.
- **Embargoes and Delayed Open Access:** Several publications were subject to embargo periods, limiting their immediate availability through open channels like Zenodo. This posed challenges for timely dissemination and slowed down progress related to several KPIs. A key lesson was the importance of coordinating with publishers early and preparing communication content in parallel, to streamline releases post-embargo. To mitigate

this issue, the consortium has started preparing and scheduling communication materials, such as social media posts, newsletter mentions, etc., in advance.

These challenges have provided valuable operational and strategic lessons. Moving forward, RESCALE will apply these lessons to strengthen coordination mechanisms, diversify content formats, and optimize engagement strategies to ensure even broader reach and sustained visibility across all stakeholder groups.

5.2 Conclusions

During the first 18 months of the RESCALE project, the consortium has made significant progress in establishing a robust and impactful dissemination and communication strategy. The activities undertaken have successfully enhanced the visibility of RESCALE's mission, methodologies, and outcomes across a large spectrum of stakeholders. These efforts were guided by the Dissemination and Communication Plan in AnnexA and directly contributed to the objectives of WP6, particularly increasing awareness, fostering stakeholder engagement and maximising project visibility across relevant communities.

Through the coordinated use of multiple communication channels such as the project website, social media platforms, newsletters, blog articles, scientific publications and other dissemination materials, RESCALE has ensured widespread access to its technical advancements and supply chain security approach. The strong emphasis on open-access availability, particularly through the dedicated Zenodo community, has further reinforced the project's commitment to transparency and knowledge sharing.

Scientific dissemination has been a key highlight of this period, with 14 high-quality peer-reviewed publications across prestigious venues, the contribution of a book chapter, and meaningful participation in leading conferences and summits. RESCALE's active engagement in EU networking events and industry summits has amplified its presence within the European cybersecurity landscape.

The use of clearly defined KPIs and a structured monitoring framework has provided the consortium with continuous feedback on dissemination effectiveness. With most KPIs for the reporting period either fully achieved or progressing as planned, the outcomes reflect a well-aligned and results-driven dissemination effort. For the KPIs that have not yet been fully achieved (e.g., Twitter/X followers) mitigation strategies are outlined in subsection 5.3.

Overall, the dissemination activities during this phase have laid a solid foundation for sustained outreach and long-term impact, ensuring that RESCALE's research and innovations continue to reach the right audiences and support the broader goals of cybersecurity in supply chains.

5.3 Future Steps

Building on the momentum established during the first 18 months, the RESCALE consortium will continue to enhance and scale its dissemination activities throughout the remainder of the project. The focus will shift toward sustaining visibility, deepening stakeholder engagement and promoting the project's technological outcomes as they mature. Key future actions include:

- **Scaling Scientific Dissemination:** The consortium will maintain a strong pipeline of publications in high-impact journals and conferences, particularly as additional technical modules are finalized and validated.
- **Strengthening Industry and Policy Outreach:** RESCALE will prioritize outreach activities currently lagging behind KPI targets, including but not limited to organizing workshops and field demonstrations, conducting MVP demonstrations and publishing press releases in national media across partner countries. These efforts will be complemented by continued engagement with policy forums and industry events to boost visibility and stakeholder alignment.
- **Collaboration with other Projects:** Existing synergies with projects like SYNAPSE will be formalized and expanded while other synergies with both Horizon and non-Horizon projects will also be pursued. As such joint dissemination activities will be performed to foster broader visibility, amplify impact and encourage cross-project knowledge exchange.
- **Increased Digital Presence on Social Media:** The project website and social media channels will continue to evolve with richer content, with the focus shifting to Twitter/X to address outreach shortcomings identified during the first year.
- **Maximizing KPI Performance:** Dissemination efforts will be continuously monitored and adapted based on KPI performance, ensuring alignment with WP6 objectives. Efforts will focus on KPIs that are currently lagging behind, such as increasing Twitter/X followers, etc.
- **Preparing for Long-Term Impact:** As the project progresses toward its final stages, focus will gradually shift to ensuring that dissemination activities support post-project sustainability. This includes open access archiving of results, long-term hosting of dissemination assets, and the development of an impact-oriented final dissemination strategy under D6.3.

These future steps will ensure that RESCALE's vision of a secure supply chain ecosystem continues to gain traction and achieves lasting impact.

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A Dissemination and Communication Plan

The Dissemination and Communication Plan presented in this annex provides the strategic foundation for RESCALE’s outreach activities. While not submitted as a standalone public deliverable, the DCP was developed internally by the consortium during the early stages of the project to guide dissemination actions across all communication channels and stakeholder groups. It outlines the project’s target audiences, outreach tools, content types, social media strategy, serving as a comprehensive reference point for all partners involved in WP6.

The DCP has played a central role in aligning outreach efforts with the project’s technical milestones and stakeholder engagement goals. Throughout this deliverable (D6.2), references have been made to the DCP to demonstrate how dissemination activities and KPI tracking have remained consistent with the project’s original communication strategy. By including the full plan here as an annex, we provide reviewers and stakeholders with visibility into the internal framework that continues to shape RESCALE’s evolving dissemination approach.

The DCP included in this annex was developed at the very beginning of the RESCALE project (M3) and is an internal report. As such, certain visual elements, tables or references may appear outdated.

1 Introduction

This document sets the foundation for reporting the organization of activities in **Task 6.1: Dissemination and Ecosystem Building**.

The proposed dissemination and communication strategy is designed to develop actions that will enable RESCALE to meet its objectives and key performance indicators as detailed in the project's Description of Action.

To effectively engage the community, the RESCALE project has crafted a comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy, which is detailed in Sections 3 and 4 of this document. Given the unique focus of RESCALE, Section 4 specifically addresses partnerships with relevant stakeholders and related EU initiatives. Section 5 summarizes and concludes the document.

In addition to outlining strategic partnerships, this document provides a structured approach to disseminating the project's objectives, methodologies and results to a broad audience. The strategy encompasses various communication channels and tools, including scientific publications, social media channels, newsletters, the project's website and traditional media, ensuring wide visibility and engagement.

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The purpose of this document is to outline the dissemination and communication plan for the RESCALE project, ensuring that all project objectives, outcomes, methodologies and advancements are effectively communicated to the relevant stakeholders. This plan is designed to create a cohesive and comprehensive communication strategy that will highlight the project's innovations and milestones. It aims to facilitate knowledge transfer and collaboration, thereby driving the adoption and integration of the RESCALE platform.

Additionally, the plan seeks to enhance the project's visibility and impact, ensuring that the achievements of RESCALE are widely recognized and utilized. Through systematic and targeted dissemination activities, this plan will support the overarching objectives of the RESCALE project and contribute to its long-term success and influence.

1.2 Intended Audience

This document is an internal report produced within the scope of WP6. The intended audience for this document includes project partners, stakeholders, policymakers, the scientific community, industry representatives and the general public who have an interest in the outcomes and impacts of the RESCALE project.

Project partners will utilize this plan to align their dissemination efforts and ensure cohesive communication strategies. Stakeholders, including collaborators and sponsors, will gain insights into how the project aims to engage with them and the broader community. The scientific community and industry representatives will find detailed information on how RESCALE's

innovations and findings are being shared, fostering potential collaborations and knowledge transfer.

Finally, the general public will be informed about the project's goals, achievements and societal benefits, promoting transparency and public engagement.

1.3 Relationship with Other Deliverables

The dissemination and communication plan is connected with other deliverables of the RESCALE project. It is closely linked with WP6 and the following project deliverables:

- **D6.2 - Dissemination Report (first version):** The results from the dissemination and communication activities carried out in accordance with the dissemination and communication plan, will be used to fulfill the requirements of D6.2 which presents the results of the project's dissemination and communication activities.
- **D6.3 - Dissemination Report (final version):** In a similar way, the results from the dissemination and communication activities will be utilized to complete the final version for the dissemination report, D6.3.

2 Dissemination and Communication Overview

The dissemination and communication strategy for RESCALE is developed across two primary domains. The first domain focuses on scientific communication, aiming to disseminate the project's scientific advancements to appropriate academic and research venues. The second domain targets industry stakeholders, where the objective is to engage these stakeholders in understanding the practical applications and benefits of RESCALE's innovations.

2.1 Dissemination and Communication Target Groups

The primary objective of the RESCALE dissemination and communication strategy is to inform stakeholders about the project's innovative ideas, services and results, encouraging their adoption and utilization.

The main strategic stakeholder groups identified for the dissemination and communication of the project are:

- **Key Actors**

- Hardware/Software providers
- Public/private organizations
- Industry institutions
- Research and innovation centers
- Policy and decision-makers
- European and global organizations
- Academic and research institutions

- **International Networks**

- Industry and technology networks
- IT and cybersecurity associations/organizations
- Service providers in relevant sectors
- Technology providers

- **Potential End-Users**

- Supply Chain Practitioners
- Industry IT/non-IT personnel
- Project managers and leaders
- Industry professionals

- **Policymakers**

- National and EU Authorities (e.g. European commission)

- Decision-makers in relevant sectors (e.g. regulators)
- **Other**
 - Standardization bodies
 - General public

2.2 Dissemination and Communication KPIs

Key performance indicators are essential tools for evaluating the effectiveness and impact of the dissemination and communication activities within the RESCALE project. By establishing clear KPIs, the project can systematically measure progress, identify areas for improvement and ensure that the dissemination efforts are aligned with the overall project goals.

KPIs provide a quantifiable way to track the reach and engagement of various dissemination activities, such as publications, events and online content. They enable the project team to assess whether the communication strategies are effectively reaching the intended audiences, including stakeholders, industry partners, policymakers and the general public.

Furthermore, KPIs facilitate accountability and transparency by providing a clear framework for reporting progress to the project partners and stakeholders. Regular monitoring and evaluation of KPIs help in making informed decisions, adjusting strategies as needed and demonstrating the value and impact of the dissemination efforts. This ongoing assessment not only supports continuous improvement but also enhances the credibility and reputation of the RESCALE project. RESCALE’s KPIs are depicted in Figure 1.

Channels	Target Audience	Activities/Measures	KPIs
Dissemination			
Scientific publications	Scientific community, Academics, Researchers	Journal publications	≥ 8 peer-reviewed publications
		International conferences	≥ 20 peer-reviewed publications
		Special issues	≥ 5 special issues / book chapters / magazine articles
International events/Demos	Scientific community, Industry associations, SW and HW providers, Policy makers	Workshops/ Field Tests	≥ 2 workshops/field tests; ≥ 40 attendees
		EU-focused events	≥ 2 demonstrations (MVP & complete solutions)
		Technical, Academic, Industrial events	≥ 6 demonstrations/webinars/training events
Networking/ Outreach	All	Interactive networking	≥ 3 EU networking events; ≥ 3 consortium led Info Days; ≥ 3 Industry exhibitions/summits
	Researchers	Collaboration with other projects & initiatives	≥ 3 synergies established with Horizon projects; ≥ 3 synergies established with other pertinent initiatives
	Policy makers, Standardisation bodies	Collaboration with policy makers and standardisation bodies	≥ 1 meeting with industry stakeholders per country represented in the consortium; ≥ 2 meetings with cybersecurity policy makers at national and EU level
Communication			
Online activities	All	Project website	Deployed by M2; ≥ 1.000 users annually; ≥ 90sec average engagement time
	Researchers	Zenodo community	≥ 1.000 views annually; ≥ 150 downloads annually (deliverables, publications & materials, e.g., presentations)
	All	Social media	≥ 100 new followers annually in Twitter and in LinkedIn; ≥ 15 posts monthly in Twitter & in LinkedIn; ≥ 4 videos annually in YouTube; ≥ 500 total views of YouTube content
	Industry Associations, SW and HW providers	Newsletters & blogs/articles	≥ 6 targeted blogs/articles annually; ≥ 3 newsletters annually
Offline activities	Industry associations, Policy makers	Presentations	≥ 6 flyers/brochures; ≥ 3 posters; ≥ 9 audience specific project presentations
	All	Traditional media	≥ 1 articles/interviews to national magazines and/or newspapers per country represented by the consortium partners

Figure 1: Dissemination and Communication Activities KPIs

All the KPIs have been taken into account and are under constant monitoring. There are 2 KPI categories, annual KPIs and overall KPIs (covering the entire project duration).

2.3 Control and Monitoring Mechanisms

To oversee all planned dissemination and communication activities, specific control and monitoring mechanisms have been developed. These mechanisms regularly track and measure the effectiveness of the project's dissemination and communication activities. These control methods are crucial as they provide valuable feedback, assess the impact for the consortium and demonstrate the project's progress.

For starters, excel files have been created and uploaded to the project's Sharepoint. These excel files track all the KPIs depicted in 1 as well as other important things regarding the project's dissemination and communication activities. Figure 2 depicts the excel file that tracks the dissemination KPIs.

DISSEMINATION					
Activity/Measures	KPIs	Target KPI	Current status	%	Done
Journal publications	≥ 8 peer-reviewed publications	8	0	0%	NO
Int. Conferences	≥20 peer-reviewed publications	20	12	60%	NO
Special issues	≥ 5 special issues/book chapters/magazine articles	5	0	0%	NO
Workshops/Field tests	≥2 workshops/special sessions; ≥40 attendees	2	0	0%	NO
EU-focused events	≥2 demonstrations (MVP and complete solutions)	2	0	0%	NO
Technical, Academic, Industrial events	≥6 demonstrations/ webinars/ training events	6	0	0%	NO
Interactive face-to-face networking	≥3 EU Networking Events	3	0	0%	NO
	≥3 consortium led Info days	3	0	0%	NO
	≥3 Industry Exhibitions/summits	3	0	0%	NO
Collaboration with other projects & initiatives	≥3 synergies established with Horizon Projects	3	0	0%	NO
	≥3 synergies established with other pertinent initiatives	3	0	0%	NO
Collaboration with Policy Makers and Standardization bodies	≥1 meeting with industry stakeholders per country represented in the consortium	11	0	0%	NO

Figure 2: Tracking Dissemination KPIs

KPI progress is presented in an organized and structured format, helping the dissemination officer to monitor clearly the progress of each KPI.

The same excel file also tracks the progress of the communication and yearly KPIs as shown in Figure 3.

COMMUNICATION					
Activity/Measures	KPIs	Target KPI	Current status	%	Done
Project website	Deployed by M2;	DONE	DONE		YES
	≥1.000 users annually; ≥90 sec average engagement time	see table below			NO
Zenodo community	≥ 1000 views annually	see table below			NO
	≥ 150 downloads annually (deliverables, publications, materials, e.g presentations)	see table below			NO
Social media	≥ 100 new followers annually in Twitter	see table below			NO
	≥ 100 new followers annually in LinkedIn	see table below			NO
	≥ 15 posts monthly in Twitter and LinkedIn	see table below			NO
	≥ 4 videos annually in YouTube	see table below			NO
	≥ 500 total views of YouTube content	500	0	0%	NO
Newsletters & blogs/articles	≥ 6 target blogs/ articles annually	see table below			NO
	≥ 3 newsletters annually	see table below			NO
Presentations	≥ 6 flyers/brochures	6	1	17%	NO
	≥ 3 posters	3	1	33%	NO
	≥ 9 audience specific project presentations	9	0	0%	NO

Figure 3: Tracking Communication KPIs

Another excel file has been created that tracks all publications made by the consortium and contains detailed information about them such as venue, type of publication (e.g. conference or journal), date of publication, description and partner responsible. This excel file is shown in Figure 4.

Paper Publications					
Date of publication	Type of paper	Name of journal / name of the conference	Publisher	Authors/Editors	Description
29/02/2024	Conference	NDSS Symposium 2024		Cristiano Giuffrida - (VUA)	Predictive Context-sensitive Fuzzing
22/05/2024	Conference	45th IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy		Cristiano Giuffrida - (VUA)	Leaky Address Masking: Exploiting Unmasked Spectre Gadgets with Noncanonical Address Translation
22/05/2024	Conference	45th IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy		Cristiano Giuffrida - (VUA)	Sticky Tags: Efficient and Deterministic Spatial Memory Error Mitigation Persistent Memory Tags
14/08/2024	Conference	33rd USENIX Security Symposium		Cristiano Giuffrida - (VUA)	InSpectre Gadget: Inspecting the Residual Attack Surface of Cross-privi Spectre v2
14/08/2024	Conference	33rd USENIX Security Symposium		Cristiano Giuffrida - (VUA)	SafeFetch: Practical Double-Fetch Protection with Kernel-Fetch Cachin
14/08/2024	Conference	33rd USENIX Security Symposium		Cristiano Giuffrida - (VUA)	GhostRace: Exploiting and Mitigating Speculative Race Conditions
01/07/2024	Conference	14th International Symposium on Business Modeling and Software Design		Andrei Costin - (Binare)	Understanding SBOMs in Real-world Systems – a Practical DevOps/Sec Perspective
01/07/2024	Conference	14th International Symposium on Business Modeling and Software Design		Andrei Costin - (Binare)	A Review On Privacy and Monetization Aspects within BCI and XR-BCI Ecosystems
01/07/2024	Conference	14th International Symposium on Business Modeling and Software Design		Andrei Costin - (Binare)	Reproducibility of Firmware Analysis: An Empirical Study

Figure 4: Tracking Publications

A third excel file that monitors all past and upcoming events has also been created as illustrated in Figure 5.

Events						
No.	Date of event	Type of event	Name of the event	Authors / providers	Description	Additional informa
1	30/07/2024	Workshops/Field test	IWAPS - 4th International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions	UPRC	The workshop is co-organized from a list of Horizon Europe/2020 projects, including RESCALE	The ARES Conference - IWAPS (4th Inte Advances on Privacy Preserving Technolog held in conjunction with the 19th Intern Availability, Reliability and Security from
2	03/11/2023	Industry Exhibitions/summits	Hardware.io 2023 Netherlands	Binare		Participation + Project visibility
3	19/03/2024	Workshops/Field test	DFRWS EU 2024 Zaragoza	Binare		Participation.

Figure 5: Tracking Events

A similar file about project synergies has been created. The social media rotation plan is also monitored this way as seen below.

COMMUNICATION - SOCIAL MEDIA ROTATION					
Month	Partner	Target posts	Actual posts	Done	Comments
Oct-23	UPRC	4	4	YES	
Nov-23	UPRC	4	4	YES	
Dec-23	UPRC	4	4	YES	
Jan-24	UPRC	4	4	YES	
Feb-24	UPRC	4	4	YES	
Mar-24	UPRC	4	4	YES	
Apr-24	UPRC	4	4	YES	
May-24	CBRL	8	8	YES	

Figure 6: Tracking Social Media Rotation

Its important to note that the figures seen previously (Figures 2 to 6) are just meant to showcase the excel files the consortium uses for monitoring the KPIs not the actual KPI numbers that RESCALE has currently achieved. The detailed KPI progress will be presented on the first Dissemination Report (D6.2).

Lastly, the WP-Statistics plugin is used for monitoring website statistics, allowing us to keep track of visiting users, views, most visited pages on the website, and other interesting statistics as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: RESCALE Website Statistics Dashboard

3 Communication Strategy

3.1 Project Logo

The RESCALE logo was created at the beginning of the project, during Month 3 to be exact. It is a combination grey and orange colors along with the RESCALE name as shown in Figure 8

Figure 8: RESCALE Logo

A logo used as the profile picture for RESCALE's social media channels has also been created, seen in Figure 9.

Figure 9: RESCALE Profile Picture

Moreover, it is of utmost importance to mention the correct wording of the project's name as "RESCALE" and not "Rescale", "rescale" or some other variation.

- **Correct Wording:** RESCALE (all letters should be capital)
- **Invalid Wording:** Rescale, rescale, etc.

Figure 10: RESCALE Wording

3.2 Project Website

The website is a crucial platform for introducing RESCALE and disseminating the project's results. Accordingly, a dedicated website has been established for the RESCALE project, providing information about its vision, objectives, use cases, results, partners and events.

The RESCALE website was developed during the initial stages of the project, specifically by Month 3, and is continuously updated with new content to maintain up-to-date interaction with the public. Through this website, basic information about the project and the relevant activities of partners is shared with the public. Key messages and non-confidential deliverables, encompassing both technical and non-technical work, are accessible to interested third parties.

The website will provide comprehensive descriptions of the project architecture, work plan and innovations. It also presents the use cases considered in the project and acknowledges the consortium partners. In addition to non-confidential deliverables, the website hosts publications and dissemination materials. Regular updates include project news and information about past or upcoming events. The primary aim of the website is to enhance the dissemination and communication activities within the project, thereby fostering greater recognition of the project and its objectives. The landing page of the website can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11: RESCALE Website Landing Page

The landing page includes the RESCALE logo, bright colors to grab the attention of visiting users, a general description of the project along with key concepts, and links to the other pages on the website.

The vision of the project and all its relevant objectives are presented to the user in the objectives page as seen in Figure 12.

Project Objectives

Figure 12: RESCALE Website Objectives Page

The objectives page will be updated with the initial and final version of the architecture of the RESCALE platform once the corresponding deliverables are ready, **D2.5 - High Level Architecture (first version)** and **D2.6 - High Level Architecture (final version)**.

The use cases page includes detailed information about the two use cases of the project by **PST** and **CC**, as depicted in Figure 13

1. Auto-Placement Security Aware Augmented Data-Flow and Infrastructure

Figure 13: RESCALE Website Use-Cases Page

The consortium page includes all the partners involved in the project, their logos in high resolution and links to their websites as illustrated in Figure 14.

Figure 14: RESCALE Website Consortium Page

Apart from general information about the project (e.g. description, objectives, vision, etc.) the website hosts most of the dissemination material of the project in the dissemination page. Figure 15 presents all the publications made by the RESCALE consortium to conferences, journals, or workshops.

RESCALE papers and publications in journals, conferences, workshops, book chapters, white papers.

Journal Papers

Conference Papers

- [Predictive Context-sensitive Fuzzing](#). Borrello, P.; Fioraldi, A.; D'Elia, D. C.; Balzarotti, D.; Querzoni, L.; and Giuffrida, C. In *NDSS*, February 2024.
- [Leaky Address Masking: Exploiting Unmasked Spectre Gadgets with Noncanonical Address Translation](#). Hertogh, M.; Wiebing, S.; and Giuffrida, C. In *S&P*, May 2024.
- [Sticky Tags: Efficient and Deterministic Spatial Memory Error Mitigation using Persistent Memory Tags](#). Gorter, F.; Kroes, T.; Bos, H.; and Giuffrida, C. In *S&P*, May 2024.

Figure 15: RESCALE Website Dissemination Page - Publications

There is also a page that includes all the deliverables of the project as rendered in Figure 16.

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)	Link
D1.1	Project handbook including Quality Management Plan, Risk Assessment and IPR management	WP1	1 - ISI	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	3	
D1.2	Data Management Plan	WP1	9 - AEGIS	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	6	
D1.3	Period 1 Project Report	WP1	1 - ISI	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	18	
D1.4	Final Project Report	WP1	1 - ISI	R – Document, report	SEN - Sensitive	36	

Figure 16: RESCALE Website Dissemination Page - Deliverables

At this point in time there are no deliverables made public yet, since the deliverables need to be approved by the EU commission once submitted. Once approved, the deliverables will be uploaded to Zenodo and corresponding links for the deliverables will be added to the website so that visiting users can view and download RESCALE’s public deliverables.

The news page contains information about important events to the project such as plenary meetings, workshops organized/co-organized by the project, important events, deliverable presentations, etc.

Lastly, the website’s contact page ensures stakeholders and the general public can contact RESCALE swiftly and receive a prompt response. The contact page is shown in Figure 17.

Contact Details

Don't hesitate to contact us!

Name *

Email *

Message *

Figure 17: RESCALE Website Contact Page

3.3 Social Media Channels

Social media channels are crucial for disseminating the project's results. RESCALE recognizes the importance of active presence and participation on social media and networking platforms (e.g., Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook) for the project's success. Accordingly, RESCALE has developed a dissemination strategy that involves all partners. By sharing progress and results at least on a weekly basis, RESCALE aims to steadily increase the number of followers, thereby enhancing the project's impact in both the scientific community and industry.

To facilitate the dissemination of results, Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and YouTube accounts have been created where important public information will be shared.

3.3.1 Twitter

Twitter boasts millions of engaged users every month from around the world, providing a significant opportunity for RESCALE to disseminate its results to a broad audience. As part of the RESCALE dissemination plan, a dedicated [Twitter Account](#) has been created to share updates, progress and important information with the public. The twitter account name for the RESCALE project is "Rescale Project Horizon EU" and the handle is "@Rescale_Horizon". The account is shown on Figure 18.

Figure 18: Twitter Account

As illustrated in Figure 18, the account includes a link to the project’s website along with a small description of the project.

3.3.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is an excellent platform for connecting with business professionals, with over 830 million users, of which a large percentage are active every month. This makes LinkedIn an ideal venue for RESCALE to disseminate its results. As part of the RESCALE dissemination plan, a dedicated [LinkedIn Page](#) about the project has been created to share updates, insights and key information with the professional community. The name for the page is “Rescale Project Horizon EU”. The page is illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19: LinkedIn Account

Project details (e.g. link to website, description of the project, etc.) have already been incorporated into the LinkedIn page.

3.3.3 LinkedIn Stakeholders Group

Apart from the project's LinkedIn page, a [LinkedIn Group](#) for the stakeholders of the RESCALE project has been created. The group allows stakeholders to easily access updates, share insights and engage in discussions related to the project's progress and findings.

Furthermore, this group facilitates real-time communication and feedback, enabling the project team to quickly address questions, gather valuable input and foster a sense of community among members. The group name is "RESCALE Project Stakeholders" as depicted in Figure 20

Figure 20: LinkedIn Stakeholders Group

For the stakeholders group, a public group has been chosen. Using a public group for RESCALE offers several advantages. Firstly, a public group increases accessibility, allowing a wider audience to join and participate in discussions without barriers. Additionally, a public group enhances transparency, demonstrating the project's commitment to open communication and community engagement. It allows potential collaborators, industry professionals and the general public to stay informed about RESCALE's progress and contribute to discussions. The visibility of a public group also aids in building the project's reputation and credibility, as it showcases an active and engaged community.

The description for the group has also been set, the purpose of the group established and the guidelines created. The group guidelines are presented below:

- **Maintain Professionalism and Respect:** Always interact with other members respectfully, even in disagreement.
- **Encourage Open and Constructive Conversations:** Promote discussions that are inclusive and productive. Share insights and feedback that contribute to mutual understanding and project advancement.
- **Respect Confidentiality:** Be mindful of the sensitivity of information shared within the group. Do not disclose or distribute any information labeled as confidential.
- **No Promotional Content:** Refrain from posting promotional material that is not directly related to the RESCALE project. Focus on content that adds value to the project and its stakeholders.
- **Adhere to Intellectual Property Rights:** Respect copyright, trademarks and other forms of intellectual property. Ensure that content shared complies with legal standards and is properly credited.
- **Report Inappropriate Behavior:** Help maintain the quality of our community by reporting any posts or behaviors that violate these guidelines.

Overall, the LinkedIn stakeholders group serves as a dynamic platform for promoting collaboration, knowledge exchange and ongoing engagement with the project's key audiences.

3.3.4 Facebook

Apart from the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, a [Facebook Page](#) has also been created as displayed in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Facebook Account

Core project information such as the project's description, website and other information have been incorporated to the Facebook page.

3.3.5 YouTube

RESCALE will also utilize a [YouTube Channel](#) to demonstrate its platform and share short and long videos explaining the project's vision, objectives, scope of the project's pilots, architecture, as well as other interesting topics. As part of the RESCALE dissemination plan, a dedicated YouTube channel has been created to visually communicate the project's progress and key information to a wider audience. The YouTube channel is displayed in Figure 22.

Figure 22: YouTube Account

The detailed plan regarding YouTube videos is explained thoroughly in Subsection 3.3.8.

3.3.6 Social Media Guidelines

RESCALE aims to achieve a total of 100 followers in LinkedIn, and 100 followers in Twitter and Facebook combined annually. In total, RESCALE will possess 600 combined followers on all social media channels by the end of the project.

To achieve 600 followers by the end of the project, RESCALE will publish 8 posts monthly on each major platform (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook). Each post published on one platform, will be published on the other platforms, albeit with small differences. Every published post will follow specific guidelines in order to maximize its impact and the visibility of the project. Specifically:

- **Hashtags:** Each post made will employ at least three hashtags, “#RESCALE”, “#HorizonEurope”, and “#CyberSecurity”. The hashtags “#SupplyChainSecurity”, “#Research” or “#Innovation” might also be used depending on the content of post. Other hashtags can also be used depending on the content of the post if they are appropriate (e.g. the hashtag #Intel used in a post about RESCALE and Intel). Hashtags help boost post visibility however the ideal number rests between three and five, without ever exceeding five in order not to overcrowd the post. Hashtags will also employ the specific format mentioned above (e.g. CyberSecurity instead of CYBERSECURITY or cybersecurity).
- **Pinned Posts:** Depending on the social media platform, one or multiple posts can be pinned on top of the profile to maximize visibility. For twitter and linkedIn, one post will be pinned at the top of the profile at all times, with new or important posts being preferred (e.g. creation of the architecture, important publication, MVP, etc.). Facebook allows up to six posts to be pinned on top of the profile.
- **Featured Posts:** In specific platforms (e.g. LinkedIn) there is a functionality that allows users to feature up to three posts on their profile. The three most important posts will be featured on the RESCALE profile at all times.

- **Tagged Partners:** If the posts revolve around the consortium (e.g. post about a partner's contribution to the project), the tagged functionality will be used, which allows users on all of these platforms to visit the partner's profile by clicking at the text.
- **Inclusion of Images:** If possible, images will be used at every post to grab attention and attract users.

3.3.7 Social Media Posts Rotation Plan

It is agreed by the RESCALE consortium that social media posts will follow a specific rotation plan. This means that for specific months, RESCALE's partners will provide the content for all the posts that will be made instead of the dissemination officer. The content for the posts can be anything relevant to the project such as:

- Relevant articles and publications to the project.
- Supply chain attack, security statistics.
- Information about components and tools that each partner is responsible for.
- Contribution of each partner to the project.
- Newly discovered supply chain vulnerabilities.
- Anything else that might be relevant to the project.

Every partner has been informed about the rotation plan and accepted the responsibility. In case that a partner doesn't send the necessary posts in a timely manner, remainders will be sent via email. If the partner still doesn't send the posts, it will be noted down to be addressed at a later time.

3.3.8 YouTube Videos

RESCALE will produce four YouTube videos annually for a total of twelve videos by the project's completion. At the same time, the project will have gathered 500 views from all its YouTube videos by the end of the project. The videos will be stored on RESCALE's Sharepoint and uploaded to the project's YouTube channel. Appropriate posts will also be made on social media to bring visibility to RESCALE's YouTube channel and boost the views of the videos.

Table 1 shows the YouTube video schedule.

Release Date	Content
December 2023	1st Video
March 2024	2nd Video
June 2024	3rd Video
September 2024	4th Video
December 2024	5th Video
March 2025	6th Video
June 2025	7th Video
September 2025	8th Video
December 2026	9th Video
March 2026	10th Video
June 2026	11th Video
September 2026	12th Video

Table 1: YouTube Videos Plan

Regarding the content of the videos, its going to vary. The core theme for some of the videos will be RESCALE's architecture, MVP and used technologies (e.g. TBOM, etc). The first video for RESCALE has already been created, uploaded to the Sharepoint and will soon be uploaded on YouTube.

3.4 Newsletters

Newsletters are crucial components of the RESCALE dissemination and communication strategy. They serve as an effective tool for regularly updating stakeholders and other relevant parties on the project's progress. By delivering timely and relevant information directly to the audience, newsletters help maintain continuous engagement and interest in the project's activities. The consistent communication fosters a sense of connection with the stakeholders, ensuring they remain informed and invested in the project's success.

Starting from Month 4, RESCALE has and will produce newsletters every four months that report on the project's news and include:

- Important project breakthroughs (e.g. design of the project's architecture, creation of a minimum viable product (MVP) etc.).
- Information about upcoming and past project events (e.g. events that the project is organizing or co-organizing, workshops, industry exhibitions, summits, demonstrations etc.).
- Research advancements, results, and publications in journals or conferences.
- Submitted deliverables to the EU commission.
- Important project meetings such as general assembly and plenary meetings.
- Other relevant news.

All the newsletters will also include core project information such as:

- The project’s logo.
- Each partner’s logo in an organized manner.
- General information about the newsletter (e.g. newsletter volume and issue, date of publication, newsletter structure, number of pages, etc.).
- QR code pointing to the project’s website.
- Information about the project manager (e.g. organization or institution leading the project and project coordinator)
- Contact information (e.g. project coordinator’s email, project’s contact emails)
- Information about the project’s communication channels (e.g. social media handles and links, website link etc.)
- Funding acknowledgment.

The newsletters will also feature colors that complement and harmonize with the logo as well as various images to capture the attention of viewers.

Three newsletters will be produced each year for a total of twelve newsletters by the end of the project. The first and second newsletters have already been created and shared with the consortium, covering the periods from October 2023 to January 2024 (M1 to M4) and February 2024 to May 2024 (M5 to M9). Figure 23 depicts part of the first published newsletter of the project.

Figure 23: Newsletter Vol.1

All newsletters will be uploaded to RESCALE’s SharePoint and Zenodo community. The newsletter page in the website will also include links that point to the newsletters in the Zenodo community so that visitors and other parties can freely download them ([Website Newsletter Page](#)). This will also help boost views and download for RESCALE’s Zenodo community. Posts will also be made to social media accounts for every published newsletter. The newsletter plan is displayed in Table 2.

Release Date	Content
January 2024	Initial Newsletter
May 2024	Quarterly Update
September 2024	Annual Review
January 2025	Quarterly Update
May 2025	Quarterly Update
September 2025	Annual Review
January 2026	Quarterly Update
May 2026	Quarterly Update
September 2026	Final Wrap-up

Table 2: Newsletter Plan

Note that its not possible to create a detailed plan of the exact content of every newsletter because that is dependant on the project’s timeline (e.g. how fast a MVP will be ready, when are the events organized etc.).

3.5 Blogs & Articles

Blogs and articles are vital parts of the RESCALE dissemination and communication plan for several reasons. By presenting complex information in a more digestible and engaging format, blogs and articles make it easier for a broader audience to understand the vision, objectives, progress and outcomes of the RESCALE project.

In the context of the RESCALE project, the news page of the website ([Website News Page](#)) will serve as the blog page, containing all published articles. This approach is advantageous because it simplifies navigation for the website visitors and allows everyone to easily access project news and articles, in one place. Furthermore using a single page for both news and blog content streamlines content management for the project team.

Six articles will be published annually on the news page of the project’s website, ensuring a total of at least eighteen articles by the project’s conclusion. These articles will cover a variety of topics, featuring:

- Summaries of deliverables approved by the EU commission.
- Highlights from significant project events (e.g. organized and co-organized events, workshops, industry exhibitions, summits, demonstrations, networking events, etc.).
- Key project breakthroughs (e.g. design of the final version of the project’s architecture, creation of a MVP, creation of a fully developed product etc.)

- Updates on general assembly or plenary meetings.
- Announcements about published dissemination material (e.g. published newsletters, posters, etc.)
- Articles describing complex technical or non-technical topics (e.g. static and dynamic code analysis methods implemented in RESCALE, how TBOM is utilized in RESCALE.
- Articles describing the components of the RESCALE platform (e.g. how they work, what they offer etc.).
- Other relevant articles about the project.

Articles will also include core information such as:

- Links to social media channels.
- Tags to differentiate them from one another.

Please note that there is no predetermined schedule for the release date of articles, as they will be published in response to noteworthy events, such as significant breakthroughs or important project milestones and events. The only schedule to be followed is the publication of six articles each year as shown in Table 3.

Project Years	Number of Articles
Year 1	6
Year 2	6
Year 3	6

Table 3: Article Plan

Two articles have already been published on the news page. Figure 24 illustrates one of them.

RESCALE 2nd Plenary meeting

The second General Assembly meeting occurred on April 15–16, 2024, six months following our inaugural kick-off meeting. During this assembly, the partners shared updates on progress across all work packages and outlined their strategies for the forthcoming months.

Figure 24: First Article

3.6 Flyers & Brochures

Flyers and brochures offer a concise and visually engaging format to showcase the project's objectives, scientific methodologies, breakthroughs, activities, events, expected outcomes and milestones. By distributing flyers and brochures at various external events, RESCALE can effectively reach academic and research institutions, industry partners and other key stakeholders, ensuring they remain informed about the project's developments.

Additionally, distributing the flyers and brochures to the general public encourages wider participation and raises awareness about RESCALE, fostering greater understanding and support for the project. Both flyers and brochures will be distributed by project partners at public events they attend such as conferences, workshops, exhibitions, summits, networking and local events to raise awareness among potential users.

The format of the flyers and brochures for the RESCALE project is carefully designed to effectively communicate key information. Outlined below are the detailed specifications for the flyer format.

- **Format:** 1-page.
- **Content:** Contains concise and impactful messages about upcoming events, key announcements and promotional information. Designed to quickly grab attention.
- **Size:** Typically A4 or A5.
- **Distribution:** Handed out in public places, included in event welcome packs, posted on bulletin boards or distributed at relevant gatherings.

The specifications for the brochure format is presented below.

- **Format:** Tri-fold (a single sheet folded into three sections).
- **Content:** Comprehensive information about RESCALE’s objectives, scientific approach, activities, milestones and achievements. Includes sections such as project overview, key innovations, consortium partners and contact details, etc.
- **Size:** A4 or letter size when unfolded.
- **Distribution:** Distributed at conferences, workshops, industry summits, meetings and other public events. Also included in direct mail campaigns and placed in display racks at strategic locations. Regularly updated to reflect the latest project achievements and results.

By the end of the project, six flyers and brochures will have been produced, three flyers and three brochures. This equates to one flyer and one brochure each year. Both will be delivered at the end of each year. However, the number of flyers and brochures may be subject to change (e.g. four brochures two flyers or the opposite). The final number for both flyers and brochures will always be six. The content of each flyer and brochure will depend on the project’s advancements up to that point. The flyer and brochure plan is presented in Table 4.

Release Date	Number of Flyers/Brochures
Month 12	2
Month 24	2
Month 36	2

Table 4: Flyer/Brochure Plan

A flyer/leaflet has already been created. It has been uploaded to RESCALE’s Sharepoint and Zenodo community. Links pointing to the flyer on the Zenodo community are also available on the newsletter page of the website ([Website Newsletter Page](#)). Figure 25 shows part of the flyer.

ABOUT RESCALE

Software is not designed and implemented nowadays from scratch, but consists of different components from multiple sources infused in the software development lifecycle (SDLC). Most of these components are not developed in-house but used as-is by a software and hardware developer.

While this approach provides reuse of already implemented functionality and, as such faster time to market, it comes with added security cost as this software supply chain is untrustworthy and relies on the typical software assessment techniques applicable to in-house software development.

RESCALE, starting 1st October 2023, aims at designing, building, and demonstrating **secure-by-design** supply chains. To this end, RESCALE will (i) automate the evaluation processes of both software and hardware components, (ii) ensure that third-party segments are free from vulnerabilities, (iii) offer effective audit procedures for cybersecurity testing, and (iv) enable the construction of secure systems with the strongest possible guarantees.

Figure 25: First Flyer

Regular updates to both brochures and flyers will be made to help sustain stakeholder interest and engagement. These updates ensure that all stakeholders are kept abreast of the project’s progress, fostering a sense of involvement and investment in the project’s success.

3.7 Posters

Posters serve as a significant tool within the RESCALE dissemination and communication strategy. They provide a visually striking and informative medium to present key aspects of the project at various events both to stakeholders and the general public. By displaying posters in prominent locations, RESCALE can effectively attract the attention of a diverse audience.

Three posters are planned for creation over the course of the project’s life cycle, equating to one poster per year. While the delivery deadlines for each poster may vary, all posters will be completed and delivered by the end of each respective year. The poster plan is presented in Table 5.

Release Date	Number of Posters
Month 12	1
Month 24	1
Month 36	1

Table 5: Poster Plan

Regarding the poster content, its going to depend on the progress of the project. The first poster has already been created and uploaded to the project’s Sharepoint and Zenodo commu-

nity. Links in the website pointing to the poster in the Zenodo community will also be made available, likely on the page containing the newsletters and flyers/brochures. Part of the poster is depicted in Figure 26.

Figure 26: First Poster

3.8 Audience Specific Presentations

To effectively disseminate RESCALE’s progress, a series of tailored presentations are planned throughout the project’s life-cycle. These presentations will target different stakeholder groups, including academic institutions, industry partners, policymakers and the general public, ensuring each audience receives relevant and consequential information.

The objectives of these presentations are to communicate the project’s goals and results, foster engagement and collaboration as well as raise awareness about the project’s impact. The presentations will be strategically timed to coincide with major project milestones and events, maintaining consistent outreach and communication.

At least nine audience specific presentations will be delivered by the end of the project. Each presentation will be evaluated based on audience engagement and feedback, ensuring the information is clearly conveyed and generates interest and potential follow-up actions. Most of the presentations will be scheduled during the first and second years of the project. During

this period, a MVP will be available, showcasing the project’s impact and demonstrating its progress.

By conducting these audience-specific presentations, RESCALE aims to keep all stakeholders well-informed and actively involved, maximizing the project’s impact and success.

3.9 Traditional Media

Engagement with traditional media aims to enhance the project’s visibility and impact. The project plans to publish at least one article or conduct one interview in national magazines and newspapers per each country represented by the consortium partners. This approach ensures that the project’s impact reaches a broad audience beyond the scientific and technical communities.

A table showcasing the partners and countries associated with the partners is presented in Table 6 (the short names of the partners have been used).

Partners	Countries
ISI, UPRC, DIE	Greece
VUA	Netherlands
UNSPMF	Serbia
EISI	Ireland
CC	Denmark
INT	Luxembourg
CBRL, S5	Cyprus
AEGIS, PST	Germany
ICERT	Italy
BNR	Finland
STS	Switzerland

Table 6: Partners and Countries

Each consortium partner will facilitate media engagements in their respective countries, including identifying suitable national magazines and newspapers, establishing contacts with journalists and coordinating interviews or article publications. Given that the consortium includes partners from eleven countries, the objective is to have eleven articles or interviews published, one in each country. Partners from the same country can collaborate to achieve more effective and meaningful results since only one article or interview is needed in every country.

The timeline for these media engagements will be aligned with major project milestones and achievements, ensuring timely and relevant coverage throughout the project’s duration. This strategic use of traditional media will help amplify the project’s messages and reach a diverse audience. The media engagements will cover various aspects of the RESCALE project, including:

- The vision of the RESCALE project.

- Issues that supply chains face nowadays (e.g. attacks on supply chains, impacts of those attacks etc.).
- How RESCALE works (e.g. demonstration of the platform, architecture etc.)
- How RESCALE helps make supply chains more secure and resilient against attacks.
- Innovation of the RESCALE project.
- State-of-the-art technologies used in the RESCALE project (e.g. machine learning (ML)/deep learning (DL), blockchain etc.).
- Scientific advancements (e.g. papers published etc.)
- Organized events (e.g. past and present events etc.).
- Involved partners (e.g. overview of the consortium etc.)
- Other relevant topics.

By securing coverage in national magazines and newspapers, RESCALE aims to raise public awareness, enhance the project's reputation, and foster broader engagement with external stakeholders. This increased visibility will contribute to a better understanding and support for the project on both national and international levels.

3.10 Press Releases

The RESCALE project has a dedicated page on its website specifically for press releases, which can be accessed at [Press Releases](#). This section serves as a central repository for several media-related content, including interviews published in national magazines or newspapers and important announcements made from consortium partners on their respective websites (e.g. such as their participation in the RESCALE project). These announcements help to reinforce the project's credibility and visibility by showcasing the active involvement of each partner.

By consolidating all press releases in one section, stakeholders can easily access and stay updated on the latest developments and media engagements related to the RESCALE project. This centralized approach not only enhances the project's communication strategy but also ensures that all significant information is readily available to the public, fostering transparency and engagement.

4 Dissemination Strategy

4.1 Open Access

One of the primary goals of the RESCALE consortium is to share knowledge on an open-access basis. The consortium will fully comply with European Commission's requirements by supporting open access for published articles. All scientific publications resulting from the project will be made openly accessible.

To achieve this goal, RESCALE will utilize the Zenodo open-access repository and make its publications available under the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) community. Apart from the publications, other material will also be uploaded to Zenodo and made freely available. The material includes:

- **Scientific Publications:** As mentioned above, all scientific publications such as journal papers, conference papers, workshop papers and whitepapers will be uploaded to Zenodo.
- **Public Deliverables:** Public deliverables that have been approved by the EU commission will also be made available on RESCALE.
- **Dissemination Material:** Including newsletters, posters, flyers/brochures and specific presentations.
- **Datasets:** Any datasets used during the project's life-cycle will be uploaded to Zenodo.

A [RESCALE Zenodo Community](#) was established in April 2024 for the project's needs, to facilitate easy access to RESCALE related materials for interested parties, as shown in Figure 27.

Planned intervention: On Wednesday June 26th 05:30 UTC Zenodo will be unavailable for 10-20 minutes to perform a storage cluster upgrade.

RESCALE Project
<https://rescale-project.eu/> Project Industrial Systems Institute ,
 Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam ,
 Dell (Ireland)

Sticky Tags: Efficient and Deterministic Spatial Memory Error Mitigation using Persistent Memory Tags
 Floris Gorter; Taddeus Kroes; Herbert Bos; and 1 other

Figure 27: RESCALE Zenodo Community

The community name is “RESCALE Project”. The community contains a project description, curation policy, some of the partners comprising the project and a link to the project’s website. Several materials produced during the project have been uploaded to RESCALE’s community, including publications, newsletters, the first poster of the project and a flyer.

RESCALE aims for 1000 views annually for all of its material on Zenodo for a total of 3000 views by the project’s end. It also aims for 150 downloads annually for 450 downloads by the project’s end.

4.2 Scientific Dissemination

For scientific dissemination, the RESCALE project relies on its members publishing in scientific venues. Scientific publications are a cornerstone of the RESCALE project’s dissemination strategy. By publishing research findings in reputable, peer-reviewed journals and conferences, the project aims to share its innovative methodologies, results and insights with the global scientific community. These publications contribute to the body of knowledge in relevant fields and enhance the project’s credibility.

The project’s scientific contributions will focus on journals and conferences related to the

project's field, preferably those with open-access proceedings. Reputable journals and conferences with high impact factors will also be preferred. The project's publications will be made available through open-access platforms, in this case RESCALE's Zenodo community as mentioned in Section 4.1. The primary audiences for the scientific communication include the scientific community, industry stakeholders and SMEs.

RESCALE's website also contains a [Publications Page](#) so that any interested party can find all the necessary details on publications related to the RESCALE project. The dissemination page on the website is comprised of two different sections, namely journal papers and conference papers. In case a partner from the consortium publishes a whitepaper, the appropriate section will also be created.

The papers on the project's website include links pointing to the uploaded publications on RESCALE's Zenodo community, allowing visitors to view and download them, thus boosting Zenodo views and downloads while allowing larger visibility of RESCALE's research methodologies and results. The metadata for each uploaded paper on Zenodo is meticulously completed during the upload process on Zenodo, guaranteeing that the papers are easily discoverable and that there are no discrepancies between different online versions.

The RESCALE consortium will have published 28 papers by the end of the project. 20 of those will be conference papers and 8 journal papers. At least 5 special issues, book chapters or magazine articles will also be published by the end of the project.

Additionally, venues where the consortium can submit papers will be identified and recommended to the partners so that they can submit potential publications. The following venues have been recommended so far:

- ACM CCS 2024.
- IEEE CSR: IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience.
- 4th International Workshop on Advances on Privacy Preserving Technologies and Solutions.

Lastly, different partners from the consortium are working together in order to create the first book chapter that will be produced during the project's life cycle.

4.3 International Events & Demos

Participation in international events and demonstrations is a crucial part of RESCALE dissemination and engagement strategy. This includes organizing workshops and field tests to showcase the project's innovations and applications in real-world settings, organizing EU focused events in the form of demonstrations to showcase the MVP of RESCALE and the complete solution, and organizing technical, academic, industrial events in the form of demonstrations/webinars/training events.

4.3.1 Workshops & Field Tests

RESCALE's workshops and field tests are designed to provide hands-on, practical experiences that showcase the project's innovative solutions and methodologies. These activities will serve as critical components of the dissemination strategy, allowing participants to directly engage with the technologies developed by the project.

The workshops will target a diverse audience, including researchers, industry professionals, and policymakers, offering them an opportunity to learn about RESCALE's advancements through interactive sessions and demonstrations. Field tests will be conducted in real-world environments to validate the effectiveness and applicability of the project's outcomes. These tests will not only demonstrate the practical benefits of RESCALE's innovations but also gather valuable feedback from end-users, which will be instrumental in refining and enhancing the solutions.

While specific plans are still in development, the overarching goal is to create immersive, memorable experiences that drive adoption and foster collaboration across different sectors. By the end of the project at least 2 workshops or field tests will have been organized by the RESCALE project with at least 40 attendees on each workshop/field test.

4.3.2 EU Focused Events

RESCALE plans to actively participate in various EU-focused events to demonstrate its MVP and complete solutions once they are ready. These events may include Horizon Europe conferences or industry summits and can provide an excellent platform to showcase the project's advancements to a broad audience of stakeholders, including policymakers, researchers and industry leaders.

Presenting at these events will not only highlight RESCALE's innovative approaches and technologies but also facilitate networking and collaboration opportunities with other European projects and initiatives. By demonstrating both the MVP and the fully developed solutions, RESCALE aims to attract interest, gather constructive feedback, and explore potential partnerships that can enhance the project's impact and reach.

By the project's end, RESCALE will have taken part in at least 2 EU focused events (1 for the MVP and 1 for the complete RESCALE solution). Since the MVP is not ready at this time, there are no specific plans for attending an EU specific event.

4.3.3 Technical, Academic, Industrial Events

RESCALE aims to actively participate in a variety of technical, academic and industrial events. The project plans to conduct at least six demonstrations, webinars or training events at the events it will participate throughout its duration. These engagements will target a diverse audience, providing them with in-depth knowledge of RESCALE's innovative technologies and methodologies.

Webinars and training sessions will offer interactive platforms for hands-on learning and direct engagement with project experts, enabling participants to gain valuable skills and insights into

both the RESCALE platform and the technologies it uses. These activities are designed to not only disseminate RESCALE's advancements but also to build a strong network of collaborators and supporters across the technical, academic and industrial sectors, enhancing the project's overall impact and reach.

4.4 Synergies with Horizon Projects and Other Initiatives

A key component of RESCALE's dissemination and communication strategy is the establishment of strategic synergies with other Horizon Europe and relevant R&I initiatives. These collaborations will serve to amplify the project's impact, support mutual knowledge exchange, and contribute to the broader European cybersecurity and supply chain security landscape.

Throughout the project lifecycle, RESCALE partners will actively identify and pursue opportunities for cooperation with other Horizon Europe projects, particularly those funded under the same or related calls, or addressing complementary domains such as cybersecurity, secure supply chains, hardware/software assurance, etc.

In addition to Horizon Europe projects, synergies will also be sought with relevant Horizon 2020 initiatives and other European or international efforts that share similar goals or target overlapping stakeholder groups. These interactions may take the form of joint dissemination activities (e.g., webinars, workshops, white papers), shared participation in stakeholder engagement events or coordinated contributions to policy and standardization discussions.

By the end of the project, RESCALE aims to establish at least three synergies with Horizon Europe or Horizon 2020 projects, and at least three additional connections with other pertinent initiatives. These synergies are not limited to existing networks of the consortium but will be actively developed based on relevance, mutual benefit and strategic alignment with RESCALE's mission.

4.5 Networking/Outreach

Networking is a pivotal aspect of RESCALE's dissemination and communication strategy, aimed at fostering direct engagement, building strong relationships and facilitating meaningful exchanges of ideas and information. The project plans to organize or participate in various networking events throughout its duration. Specifically:

- At least 3 EU networking events, 3 consortium led info days and 3 industry exhibitions or summits will be organized or attended, for a total of 9 events.
- 2 meetings with cybersecurity policy makers at national and EU level will take place.
- 1 meeting with industry stakeholders per country represented in the consortium will be held, for a total of 11 meetings.

4.5.1 Cybersecurity Dissemination

From a cybersecurity perspective, ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and implementing robust defences against attacks is critical for supply chains targeted by the RESCALE project. The RESCALE consortium includes several key cybersecurity services and tools providers, which are integral to communicating the project's results to prospective and existing stakeholders.

To present the outcomes of RESCALE to the broader cybersecurity community the project will actively participate in industry forums and conferences. The project continuously tries to identify opportunities for participation in events that can positively impact the project. Details of events are presented in a Section below.

5 Conclusion

The RESCALE dissemination and communication plan provides a structured framework for effectively disseminating and communicating information about the project. This document outlines a detailed schedule for newsletters, the establishment and management of social media accounts, potential synergies with other projects, the engagement strategies for various stakeholders through traditional media and interactive events, etc.

The plan also emphasizes the importance of face-to-face networking through participation in EU networking events, consortium-led info days and industry exhibitions. These activities are designed to promote direct interaction, gather valuable feedback, and build strong relationships with key stakeholders.

KPIs have been established to measure the effectiveness of these dissemination efforts, ensuring that the project's communication strategies are aligned with its goals and objectives. Regular monitoring and adaptive management will enable the project team to make data-driven adjustments, enhancing the overall impact and reach of the dissemination activities.

Furthermore, the control and monitoring mechanisms detailed in this plan provide a robust framework for tracking progress, evaluating success and ensuring accountability. By maintaining comprehensive documentation and reporting, the project can demonstrate transparency and foster trust among stakeholders.

In summary, the RESCALE dissemination and communication plan is a comprehensive and strategic approach to ensuring that the project's developments are effectively communicated to all relevant parties. This plan not only supports the immediate dissemination goals of the RESCALE project but also lays the foundation for its long-term success and sustainability.